

ANNUAL REPORT 2010

DIRECTOR'S MESSAGE

In February this year, I took over from Kathleen Smith as Director of NESCent. NESCent was—and still is—in good shape: its science programs are running smoothly and we are seeing an increase in international participation and career-stage diversity amongst our participants; our informatics team is a powerhouse of activity, and they contribute significantly to the Center and the broader scientific community; and the Education and Outreach Group continues to inform (and, in the process, excite) teachers, students and the lay public about evolutionary science.

As part of the change in leadership, this year saw some attendant changes in emphasis: we are looking more closely at interdisciplinarity in our proposals, and we are identifying ways that the Center can foster international links. We have stepped up our efforts to develop collaborations with other centers of equivalent scope, and we have identified certain initiatives – particularly, evolutionary medicine, astrobiology, and biodiversity – where we feel that NESCent can help develop a synthetic approach to research and education.

As part of our ongoing assessment, we have also identified challenges. Significant amongst these, and one that I am most concerned about, is the low participation of underrepresented minorities in our science programs. We have tried to think creatively about ways we can cater to, and engage with, groups that are poorly served, both in terms of science education and the resources that they may have access to. We have initiated an Ambassadors program to support science communities in other countries. Nationally, we have programs to help faculty and students from minority-serving institutions with opportunities that most academics at Research 1 universities take for granted – attendance at conferences, workshops or courses, and the chance to interact with scientists from other institutions. But we need to do more.

A second challenge relates to NESCent's sustainability after the current round of funding ends. I have little doubt that NESCent is a relevant and important resource for the evolutionary science community. At the recent Evolution meeting in Portland, a quick show of hands revealed that practically everyone had heard of NESCent and, more encouragingly, a very large majority had participated at NESCent. I am certain that NESCent will continue to work well with its constituencies, and will continue to adapt to the needs of the community. But the vagaries of funding mean that we cannot count on a free ride.

In the coming year, I will personally focus my energies in two areas. First, I will work to increase the participation of underrepresented minorities in NESCent's programs. Second, I want to ensure that NESCent has the highest likelihood of securing a future beyond December 2014.

Allen Rodrigo
24 September 2010

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Center-wide Developments and Administration

We began Year 6 with a new Director (Allen Rodrigo) and a new Associate Director of Science (Susan Alberts). To coincide with the renewal in funding, we felt that it was appropriate to re-evaluate NESCent's mission. The result was a new mission statement that takes account of NESCent's evolving scope and areas of strategic focus:

NESCent promotes the synthesis of information, concepts and knowledge to address significant, emerging, or novel questions in evolutionary science and its applications. NESCent achieves this by supporting research and education across disciplinary, institutional, geographic, and demographic boundaries.

The new statement gives equal weight to both research in synthetic evolutionary science, and education. It also emphasizes NESCent's role in crossing boundaries. As a consequence, we have made changes in the way we (a) administer our education and outreach program, (b) evaluate project proposals, (c) identify targeted activities, and (d) develop our educational and outreach activities, to reflect our new mission.

It is important to note two important directions that NESCent intends to develop later this year, and in Year 7. First, we expect to engage with other synthesis centers and centers of equivalent scope, nationally and internationally, on several fronts, including the development of research and education ties, and the sharing of resources, particularly cyberinfrastructural and informatics resources. Second, we strongly support, and are involved with, the Dimensions in Biodiversity program, at both the grassroots and strategic levels.

Administratively, we are in the process of convening an Oversight Committee consisting, in part, of senior administrators from Duke University, the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, and North Carolina State University. New members have been recruited to our Advisory Board, and we will continue to recruit until we have 20 board members.

One significant loss will be the departure of our Assistant Director of Administration, Karen Henry, at the end of this year. We will begin a search for her replacement in October 2010. We place on record our gratitude for her years of service at NESCent.

Science and Synthesis

NESCent's Science program in Year 6 represented a significant expansion of the foundation established over years 1 through 5. In addition to continuing our existing science programs, we added several new programs. At the same time, we maintained the lively in-house community of scientists that characterizes the NESCent environment.

Specifically, our Year 6 programs encompassed the following activities.

Working Groups and Catalysis Meetings

We received 16 Working Group proposals and 11 Catalysis Meeting proposals in 2010, a substantial but manageable number for us. Of these, 7 Catalysis Meetings and 6 Working Groups were approved by the board.

Long-term sabbaticals

We received 7 requests for year-long sabbaticals at the Center this year. Four scholars are already in residence, and 2 more are under consideration; whether we accommodate one or two more will depend on available space.

Postdoctoral Fellowships

We received 37 applications for Postdoctoral Fellowships; 8 were awarded and 5 were accepted. These scholars join the current set of Postdoctoral Fellows to make our largest in-house set of Postdoctoral Fellows so far.

New Initiative: Graduate Fellowships

We initiated our Graduate Fellowship program this year, and currently have five Graduate Fellows pursuing a range of research projects. Four are resident at the Center for all or part of the semester, and the fifth will work closely with a Working Group.

New Initiative: Targeted Research Areas

We introduced two targeted initiatives to jumpstart new areas of evolutionary synthesis, Astrobiology and Evolutionary Medicine. We will pursue these through a combination of co-sponsored meetings, workshops, symposia, Working Groups and Catalysis Meetings over the next year.

New Initiative: Postdoctoral Exchange Program and Postdoctoral Symposium

These programs are intended to enhance the experience of our Postdoctoral Fellows and at the same time increase interactions across the synthesis centers. In a recent supplement request, we proposed an annual Symposium designed to allow postdoctoral scholars at the synthesis centers to share their research progress. The Exchange Program will offer fellows at any synthesis center to request a short-term residence at one of the other synthesis centers. This latter program is currently in development.

Our focus for Year 7 will be to bring to fruition the targeted science initiatives that were proposed in the renewal and initiated in year 6. We will also continue and build on the momentum of successful past activities.

Education and Outreach

NESCent's Education and Outreach efforts in Year 6 built on the foundation established over years 1 through 5 – continuing to deliver the products and activities that have successfully impacted the scientific and education communities and the general public, while actively pursuing new education and outreach initiatives that will extend our reach and advance our mission of promoting synthetic evolutionary science across disciplinary, institutional, geographic, and demographic boundaries.

Broadly, our Year 6 activities included projects serving:

The education community and general public

We organized symposia and workshops on evolution and evolution education for K-12 teachers and college/university instructors, developed and disseminated content and resources to enhance the teaching of evolution, and promoted awareness and understanding of evolution through public events such as our Darwin Day activities.

The scientific community

We maintained and expanded our broad initiatives in NESCent postdoctoral professional development, undertook an aggressive effort to survey the scientific community on gaps and perceived needs with respect to extant short courses on evolution, and solicited proposals to fill those gaps via NESCent-sponsored courses.

Underrepresented minorities

We continued our successful program of outreach activities at SACNAS, provided travel awards for undergraduates and MSI faculty to attend a national evolution conference, provided mentorship and professional development for undergraduates attending this conference, and continued our targeted sabbatical program.

Our focus for Year 7 will be on continuing to build on the momentum of successful past activities, while expanding our outreach to a broader national and international audience through initiatives such as our new NESCent Ambassadors program, MSI Guest Lectureship program and an exciting and novel direction for future Darwin Day activities.

Informatics

NESCent's Informatics activities in Yr 6 continue to strategically mix software development, community coordination, human capacity building, and organizational leadership to meet the informatics requirements of visiting and resident scientists, on the one hand, and the larger needs of the synthetic evolutionary biology community, on the other.

Our major accomplishments in Year 6 include:

Sponsored science

This year, NESCent will have completed the software development on two uniquely valuable databases built to support specific working groups: the Primate Life History Database and the Mammalian Feeding Database, as well as launched a new database project for a working group studying the evolution of vision in vertebrates.

Center operations

The administrative database used for management of all projects and activities has undergone substantial enhancement, particularly in tracking scientific products (e.g. papers, software) and collecting assessment data (e.g. for the Science of Science project). A dedicated videoconferencing facility has been built to better facilitate remote collaborations.

Cyberinfrastructure and community resources

NESCent now hosts TreeBASE, a major community resource, and achieved the release of a major rewrite that had been many years in the making. NESCent has helped to launch a nonprofit Phyloinformatics Research Foundation to provide future organizational stability and strategic direction for TreeBASE, the Tree of Life Web Project and similar community resources. NESCent hosted a variety of workshops with significant outcomes, including a series that led to a strategic plan for the digitization and mobilization of biocollections data, and a major vertebrate anatomy ontology workshop. A hackathon to enhance the tools available for evolutionary analysis within the Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD) is planned for November.

Human capacity building

NESCent organized or co-sponsored five short courses on evolutionary informatics, and organized nine summer internships in informatics (six through the Google Summer of Code and three through other collaborations). NESCent sponsored and organized a highly successful inaugural iEvoBio conference on collaborative, open-source software development in evolution and biodiversity. The Center has also helped to organize multiple sessions at the upcoming TDWG Biodiversity Standards conference, and two international GMOD meetings in support of open development and standards.

Our activities in Year 7 will include three areas of emphasis. **One**, we will be updating the suite of informatics services and technologies we provide sponsored scientists, across the board. We will work closely with other synthesis centers to exchange experience, and identify shared needs and opportunities. **Two**, we expect to launch a number of new informatics courses, scale up our summer internship program, and continue to nurture the iEvoBio satellite conference. **Three**, we will continue to play a leadership role for the evolutionary biology community in the development of standards and infrastructure for data preservation, interoperability, and reuse.

Science Communications

To highlight some of the more significant and novel evolutionary questions addressed by NESCent-sponsored science and make the results accessible to broader audiences, we work with both in-house and visiting scientists to translate NESCent-sponsored research for scientists and educators in other disciplines, the media, and the general public.

Major activities in year 6 include:

Increasing the visibility of sponsored science in mainstream media outlets

In the past year we have translated nearly twenty NESCent-sponsored publications into news releases, which we distribute to reporters via an online news service run by the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS). These releases frequently feature direct quotes and commentary from scientists collaborating across multiple disciplines, nations, and institutions.

Enhancing NESCent's visibility within the scientific community via our quarterly newsletter

Members of NESCent's scientific community and other interested readers can subscribe to our quarterly newsletter (www.nescent.org/news/Newsletter_NESCent.php) to receive news about research and training opportunities and upcoming events.

Raising awareness of research and opportunities in evolution (both at NESCent and elsewhere) using social networking tools
NESCent has also joined a host of other scientific centers and organizations in making use of social media to enhance our presence on the web. Interested readers can subscribe to the NESCent Twitter feed (<http://twitter.com/NESCent>) to get daily news and announcements. We are now up to 430 followers, a group that includes researchers, educators, reporters, and members of the general public from across the globe.

Our goal for year 7 will be to continue to reach new target audiences and forge new links to the science and journalism communities, as well as the general public. In the coming year we plan to launch or build on a number of programs, including a journalist-in-residence program and a conference travel fellowship for evolutionary bloggers.

Assessment

NESCent's Assessment activities during the previous year combined strengthening our current assessment portfolio while developing new initiatives to measure our impact on the broader scientific community.

Our Year 6 activities included four major initiatives:

Improving the quantity and quality of data collection and management

A number of advancements were made to the NESCent Administrative Database that allowed for the collection of new types of data and consistent reporting of previously identified data categories. Our efforts have essentially automated our internal evaluation program (Tier 1) allowing for increased focus on NESCent's impact on the broader scientific community and the landscape of science.

Developing a framework for institutional assessment

As stipulated in the PTC, we are required to provide a summative assessment of NESCent's impact on the scientific community. This year, we have tried to define the best strategy to achieve this, given the relatively unique nature of NESCent's mission. We have decided that an appropriate strategy is Hypothesis Driven Assessment (HDA). This approach uses existing and new metrics of scientific success to test hypotheses of interest.

Developing collaborations to help us advance our assessment program

One of the challenges we face is the absence of expertise within NESCent on the science and practice of assessment. Consequently, we have spent time trying to develop links with researchers in the field of assessment science.

Collection of survey data for the Science of Science program

We are routinely surveying all groups that come to NESCent, as part of the Science of Science program. We are on-track to obtain a good sample size for most groups (excluding Hackathons) by the end of 2011. Preliminary results are discussed below.

We have three planned outcomes for Year 7:

- To confirm collaborations on developing Tier 2 assessment methods, using NESCent's programmatic options, e.g., graduate student fellowships, short-term visitorships, and working groups.
- To finalize a plan for Tier 2 summative assessment
- To complete the majority of data collection for Tier 3 assessment

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Center-wide Developments

One of our first tasks this year was to revise NESCent's mission to reflect the evolving scope of NESCent's activities and to more explicitly capture NESCent's strategic imperatives. The new mission statement, developed in consultation with the Operations Committee, NESCent Advisory Board, and the NSF, reads:

“NESCent promotes the synthesis of information, concepts and knowledge to address significant, emerging, or novel questions in evolutionary science and its applications. NESCent achieves this by supporting research and education across disciplinary, institutional, geographic, and demographic boundaries.”

Whereas our earlier mission statement speaks of “research in evolutionary biology,” the new mission refers to evolutionary science, thus drawing the distinction between evolution as a discipline of interest only to biologists, and the new “evolution” that is also a part of linguistic, cultural and social studies. Similarly, the new mission statement gives equal weight to NESCent's support for both research and education. Finally, the new statement speaks of crossing boundaries – in particular, disciplinary, institutional, geographic and demographic boundaries.

We firmly believe that a good mission statement clarifies the aims and purpose of an organization. For this reason, we have chosen to use our statement to guide our activities. These activities are described more fully in the following sections of this report. Here it is useful to list just some of the initiatives and developments at NESCent that relate to the goals of research and education, interdisciplinarity, international participation, and diversity.

We now review proposals for Catalysis Meetings and Working Groups on interdisciplinarity, international participation, and demographic/career-stage diversity, in addition to the quality of the science.

- We are expanding our service to Minority Serving Institutions and Faculty, by providing support to our resident scholars to visit MSIs.
- We are expanding our Darwin Day program to reach communities that are not served by universities, museums, or other institutions.
- We have begun cultivating links to international institutions of equivalent scope. We have met with the Canadian Society for Ecology and Evolution and we have invited them to participate in some of our activities.
- As part of the renewal, we now have the first batch of NESCent Graduate Student Fellows, who are working with resident scientists at NESCent or with NESCent working groups.

- We have instituted a NESCent Ambassador program, to deliver courses and support to countries that may lack the requisite skills for data analysis.

There are two other areas where NESCent intends to make a difference. The first involves the development of links with other synthesis centers and centers of equivalent scope and mission. This year, we organized and hosted a meeting of Education, Outreach and Communications staff from the NSF funded synthesis centers (NESCent, NCEAS, NIMBioS, iPlant) as well as NEON, BioSynC (the Biodiversity Synthesis Center) and AIBS to explore possible areas of overlap and potential collaboration and leveraging of efforts. Looking ahead, we are developing three additional initiatives for cross-center activities:

- We are organizing an inter-center postdoctoral symposium, bringing together postdoctoral scholars from all the synthesis centers. The hope is that this will be the first of an annual series of postdoctoral symposia, rotating amongst the different centers.
- We are instituting a postdoctoral exchange program, whereby postdoctoral scholars from one synthesis center can spend time at another. The idea is to increase the potential for cross fertilization.
- We are organizing a cross-center cyberinfrastructure workshop, to discuss common problems, share solutions, and avoid the duplication of cyberinfrastructural resources.

Second, NESCent is strongly supportive of new initiatives in biodiversity research, and the NSF Dimensions in Biodiversity (DIB) program. In this regard:

- NESCent has hosted two workshops on digitization of collections
- NESCent has hosted the biological charrette for DIB
- NESCent has helped organize the Cyberinfrastructure for DIB workshop, and is also participating in the “Future Directions in Systematics and Biodiversity Research” workshops.

1.2 NESCent Activities in Relation to the “General Programmatic Terms and Conditions”(PTC) Document

The PTC document lists a number of initiatives and programs that extend NESCent's mission beyond those developed in Years 1 – 5 of the Center. In the following sections, we briefly describe what we have done to address these new requirements. More details can be found in the relevant sections of this annual report.

1.2.1 Targeted catalysis meetings (3 in years 2-4)

We have identified the theme for the first catalysis meeting: Astrobiology, Origins of Life and Synthetic Biology. This theme was identified in consultation with our Advisory Board, as one of three areas of emerging and significant interest. Dr Lynn Rothschild, NASA AMES, has agreed to develop this program with us, and will visit NESCent between 5 – 7 Oct 2010 to begin planning the program.

To identify other themes that may be important for catalysis and synthesis, we have solicited input from the evolutionary science community. These ideas will be discussed with the Advisory Board when they meet next year.

1.2.2 Targeted initiatives (2 in years 1-3)

In the PTC, provision is made for targeted initiatives that “span multiple activities ... around a common theme.” We have initiated one targeted activity around the theme of Evolutionary Medicine and Human Evolution (see Science and Synthesis section for details).

Again, we will develop other themes based on input from the community and advice from the Advisory Board.

1.2.3 Activities in the areas of Science Education, Science Journalism, Citizen Science, Science Pedagogy

NESCent will support a journalist-in-residence in Year 2. We have identified a list of names, and we will make a decision on whom to invite in consultation with the Operations Committee. We are targeting early- to mid-career freelance journalists and we will provide support equivalent to a targeted sabbatical (see Communications section).

We also have an existing Working Group on “Communicating Human Evolution” which is focused entirely on activities related to science education and pedagogy, science journalism and citizen science (see Education and Outreach section).

We are planning to move our Darwin Day program beyond North Carolina, to communities where there is little or no access to the activities that are typically run at large institutions and universities to celebrate evolutionary science.

Finally, conversations are ongoing with Dr. David Sloan Wilson (PI of the Integrating evolutionary theory with behavioral economics working group) about future partnerships between NESCent and Wilson’s EvoS (Evolutionary Studies) consortium. These partnerships will focus on evolution education/outreach projects and activities.

1.2.4 New assessment activities

We have been actively collecting data for our multitiered Assessment and “Science of Science” activities. Here, we note that we are on track to deliver a plan and protocol for summative (Tier 2) assessment by the end of Year 7 of NESCent (i.e., Year 2 of the current renewal). Briefly, the approach we intend to take is a hypothesis-driven assessment (HDA) plan that builds on the use of existing and new metrics of scientific activity (see Assessment section).

1.2.5 Ongoing project oversight

The new Oversight Committee will be formed by the end of Year 6, and the Vice-Provost of Research at Duke University will send out invitations to senior managers at partner institutions in October 2010. The NESCent Advisory Board has elected a chair and vice-chair to sit on the Oversight Committee. These are Joseph Graves, Jr. and Maria Orive, respectively (see Administration section).

The Director speaks with the cognizant NSF program officer monthly. Additionally, NSF program officers visit NESCent when the Advisory Board meets. The Director visits NSF at least twice a year, typically with one or more of the Associate Directors.

1.3 This report

In compiling this report, we are guided by the requirements in Section 5 of the PTC. Nonetheless, we are conscious of the need to be concise. By necessity, what we provide are only highlights.

The next sections describe our Year 6 activities and accomplishments in Science and Synthesis, Education and Outreach, Informatics, Assessment, and Communications. We also discuss our plans for Year 7, within each of these sections.

In the last section, we describe staffing, the new administrative committees, and changes to administration.

The appendices contain quantitative details of participants, demographics, projects, and outputs, as required under Section 5 of the PTC.

The last pages of the report contain the budget and the budget justification.

2. SCIENCE AND SYNTHESIS

2.1 Year 6 activities

2.1.1 Ongoing Activities

In year 6, NESCent’s Calls for Proposals attracted 75 proposals for Working Groups, Catalysis Meetings, Sabbaticals, Postdoctoral Fellowships, or Courses. Decisions on 25 of these 75 are pending, and will be final by mid-October 2010 after the Fall meetings of the Advisory Board and the Operations Committee. Of the remaining 50, 14 were supported (see Appendices for summary).

We also attracted 22 applications for Short-term Visits and Graduate Fellowships in year 6. Of these 22, 15 have been supported and 5 are pending, having just been submitted. The complete list of NESCent scientific projects funded in year 6 is given in the Appendices.

In the aggregate as of September 1st, NESCent supported 30 scientific meetings in year 6 (24 Working Group meetings and 6 Catalysis meetings), involving 408 visitors. In addition we hosted 9 meetings and 123 visitors by a variety of groups involved in evolutionary synthesis not supported by NESCent funds. A complete list of meetings at NESCent in year 6 is given in Appendix #. Figure 1 (below) shows the number of participants at NESCent on a weekly basis.

2.1.2 Science Highlights

A few examples of exciting results in 2010 include:

- **Catalysis Meeting: Human evolution and adaptation to high-altitude hypoxia.** PI(s): Cynthia M Beall (Case Western Reserve University), Peter Robbins (Oxford University). This catalysis meeting brought together an international team of physical anthropologists, human physiologists, human geneticists and other scientists to explore how native highlanders have evolved to differ from their low-altitude ancestors. Their first papers are now coming out, including a study identifying a gene that allows Tibetans to live and work more than two miles above sea level without getting altitude sickness. Originally working separately, the authors of the study first put their findings together during a March 2009 catalysis meeting at NESCent. When they shared their findings, they suddenly realized that several sets of studies pointed to the same culprit — a gene on chromosome 2, called EPAS1, involved in red blood cell production and hemoglobin concentration in the blood. The paper, titled “Natural selection on EPAS1 (HIF2) associated with low hemoglobin concentration in Tibetan highlanders,” appeared in the June 7, 2010 issue of Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences (PNAS). Their results have also appeared in the New York Times and the Discovery Channel.

Figure 1: Number of Visiting Scientists Per Week

- Working Group: Evolutionary ecology of primate life histories. PI(s): Karen Strier (University of Wisconsin-Madison), Susan Alberts (Duke University). This working group brought together a group of scientists interested in standardizing, sharing, and preserving decades of painstakingly-collected field data on wild primates. The five-year effort has resulted in the Primate Life History Database (<http://plhdb.org/>), a collaborative and comprehensive database containing life history data collected from long-term field studies of seven species of lemurs, monkeys and apes. In addition to preserving and standardizing data from some of the longest-running field studies of their kind—ranging from 24 to 45 years in duration—the database will facilitate comparative analyses of primate evolution and ecology. Current analyses are exploring mortality patterns and variations in fertility across multiple species, with implications for both conservation and human evolution. The Primate Life History Database currently contains information for more than 3,300 individual monkeys and apes. The data were collected over several decades by researchers at UW-Madison, Duke, Princeton University, the University of North Carolina-Charlotte, Iowa State University, Columbia University, the University of Calgary, the Dian Fossey Gorilla Fund International and the Atlanta Zoo, and the Institute of Primate Research at the National Museums of Kenya. The design and development of the database is described in a paper published online Apr. 22 in the journal *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*.
- NESCent postdoctoral fellow Julie Meachen-Samuels published a paper in the July 2nd 2010 issue of the journal PLoS ONE that received a fair amount of attention. Titled “Radiographs reveal exceptional forelimb strength in the saber-toothed cat, *Smilodon fatalis*,” the paper reports that saber-toothed cats had exceptionally strong forelimbs compared to their feline cousins. Meachen-Samuels’ results have been featured in *Science Magazine*, *Discover Magazine*, and *MSNBC News*.
- NESCent postdoctoral fellow Stephen Smith and colleagues published a paper in the March 15 issue of *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* suggesting that flowering plants may be considerably older than previously thought. To trace the origins of flowering plants, the researchers used genetic comparisons of living plants and clues from fossils to reconstruct the relationships among more than 150 terrestrial plant species. If confirmed, their results would push back the age of angiosperms to 215 million years ago, some 25 to 75 million years earlier than either the fossil record or previous molecular studies suggest. More importantly, the authors say, the findings fuel ongoing debates over different approaches to dating the tree of life.

2.1.3 Application and Review Process

In addition to developing a new proposal mechanism for graduate students applying for NESCent Graduate Student Fellowships, we have also explicitly encouraged that all proposals identify international participation, the involvement of graduate students, interdisciplinarity, and demographic diversity, within the framework of their project. We have also asked the Advisory Board to review proposals in the light of these criteria.

2.1.4 The NESCent In-house Community and Postdoctoral Development

We have maintained a vibrant and collegial community of in-house scientists. During year 6, the Center has hosted 15 postdoctoral fellows, 6 sabbatical scholars, 2 Triangle research fellows, 10 short-term visitors, 5 graduate students, and several visiting and resident scientists.

NESCent has continually worked to improve the mentoring and professional development program for our postdoctoral fellows. Each entering postdoctoral fellow meets with a mentoring committee to discuss the postdoctoral fellow’s research plans, NESCent expectations, local and other resources; and the development of a written mentoring plan for each postdoctoral fellow.

In addition, we run a postdoctoral professional development program that, this year, included:

- A three-day NESCent Postdoctoral Retreat. This is the second year we have run this retreat. It included a half-day workshop on “Effective College Teaching,” targeted sessions on “Communicating with the Media and Public,” “NSF Grant Writing and Submission,” “Managing Professional and Personal Lives,” and “Understanding and Realizing Your Scientific Goals,” as well as multiple structured sessions to discuss research.
- A Postdoctoral Professional Development Seminar Series throughout the year, including recent sessions on “Interviewing for a Faculty Position,” “Negotiating Your First Faculty Position,” “Starting and Managing a Laboratory,” “Mentoring Students and Postdoctoral Fellows,” “Science and Policy,” and “Conflict Resolution and Management.”

2.1.5 New Initiatives

In Year 6, we initiated several important new scientific activities. Some of these initiatives – targeted catalysis meetings, targeted working groups, and the Graduate Fellowship Program - were proposed in the grant renewal. Our Inter-center Postdoctoral Symposium and Postdoctoral Exchange Program have been developed in year six.

We initiated a Graduate Fellowship Program, putting out our first call for proposals in July 2010. Fellows receive one semester of support from NESCent, and devote

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100% of their time during that semester to the proposed activity. All Fellows spend some time at NESCent during their fellowship semester, but some do so only as part of a Working Group, while others spend time as residents for up to several months. Up to eight Fellows will be supported each year. Incoming Graduate Fellows, like incoming Postdoctoral Fellows, must present a mentorship plan for their fellowship that outlines how their work at NESCent will be supervised by a NESCent scientist or by a working group. Our first round of awards has been granted to 5 graduate students from 5 different institutions. Two of the Fellows are associated with Working Groups; in these cases, the Fellowship enhances and significantly extends work that the Fellow was already doing with the Working Group, strengthening collaborative ties between the Fellow and members of the Working Group. The other three Graduate Fellows are working with in-house NESCent scientists, one with a sabbatical scholar and two with NESCent postdocs.

We introduced two targeted initiatives to jump-start new areas of evolutionary synthesis. These are also described in the Introduction. As proposed in the grant renewal, we developed these in consultation with our Advisory Board and Operations Committee, working with ideas that came out of our first Community Summit.

The first area that we have identified for a targeted initiative is Astrobiology, the Origins of Life and Synthetic Biology. Dr. Lynn Rothschild, of the NASA Ames Research Center, is collaborating with us on this targeted initiative. Dr. Rothschild is making her first visit to NESCent in early October 2010, in order to start planning our activities for this initiative.

The second targeted initiative we have identified is Evolutionary Medicine and Human Evolution. For this theme, we have supported, or are involved in, the following activities:

- Aug 6th- 8th, 2010 – Workshop on Evolutionary Medicine, New Zealand. NESCent sponsored the attendance of Carl Bergstrom, Fred Nijhout and Allen Rodrigo. Organized by Peter Gluckman, Randy Nesse, Allen Rodrigo.
- Oct. 8th, 2010 – EvoMed “mini-camp” – One day workshop for medical practitioners and clinicians on evolutionary biology to be held at NESCent. Organized/led by Randy Nesse, Greg Wray.
- Oct. 13th, 2010 – Participation in Institute of Medicine-organized meeting “Evolution in the Medical Curriculum” in Washington, DC.

- Feb., 2011 – NESCent’s Communicating Human Evolution working group is organizing a symposium on human evolution at the AAAS annual meeting in Washington, DC and a workshop for journalists on communicating human evolution at the Smithsonian Institution.
- Summer, 2011 – Building on the Oct., 2010 EvoMed “mini-camp,” NESCent will co-sponsor a two week, CME workshop on evolutionary biology for medical practitioners and clinicians, to be held on Mt. Desert Island, ME.
- Support for a working group on Evolutionary Mismatch (PI: Sloan Wilson) from the July 2010 round of proposals.

We are developing two programs designed to enhance scientific interactions between the synthesis centers and to enhance the postdoctoral experience:

- One is a Postdoctoral Symposium, which will include postdoctoral fellows from all of the National Synthesis Centers, and will also include selected invitees from international synthesis centers, such as the Canadian Institute for Evolution and Ecology. Planning for the first symposium is underway, with a target date of mid-April 2010.
- Second, a new Postdoctoral Exchange Program is designed to allow postdoctoral fellows at any one of the synthesis centers to spend time in residence at one of the other synthesis centers. Our initial discussions about this with other synthesis centers have been quite positive, and we foresee that this program will be off the ground within the next year.

2.2 Year 7 Activities

In year 7, we will bring to fruition the first targeted initiatives in Astrobiology/Origins of Life/Synthetic Biology and Evolutionary Medicine.

We anticipate a lively continuation of Working Group and Catalysis meetings in year 7. Twenty groups are continuing from previous years, and we project another ~10 groups initiated in year 7, based on our most recent round of award decisions.

In year 7 we will have our largest set to date of resident sabbatical scholars, with five beginning a year-long residency in September 2010 and an additional four applications pending for 2010-2011.

We will also host the first Postdoctoral Symposium for Fellows from NCEAS, NESCent, NIMBios, iPlant, BioSynC, and the Canadian Institute for Ecology and Evolution, which will take place at NESCent.

3. EDUCATION AND OUTREACH

3.1 Year 6 Activities

3.1.1 Outreach to the education community and general public

In partnership with AIBS, our annual Evolution Symposium was organized as part of the National Association of Biology Teachers (NABT) annual conference. Entitled “Evolution in Extreme Environments,” it featured four internationally known researchers and, for the first time was also accessible via live webcast. We developed, produced and distributed a CD-ROM of learning resources and offered a half-day, hands-on teacher workshop to compliment the symposium.

Other activities included:

- A three-day summer workshop, as well as multiple short talks, workshops and presentations for high school teachers on effective teaching strategies for evolution.
- Our successful “Evolution in the News” feature and podcast series, in partnership with the Understanding Evolution website.
- The Communicating Human Evolution working group led by Norman Johnson, focusing entirely on activities related to science education and pedagogy, science journalism and citizen science. Some of the ongoing activities from this working group include:
 - Developing teacher workshops, teacher certification processes and online courses related to human evolution;
 - Developing a standardized list of core concepts and goals for teaching human evolution at different grade levels;
 - Securing a grant to fund development of a Human Evolution instructional website;
 - Developing a symposium on Human Evolution to be held at the 2011 AAAS meeting in Washington, DC, and an complimentary workshop for journalists on communicating human evolution, to be held at the Smithsonian Institution;
- Organizing a one-day Evolutionary Medicine “Mini-Camp” for medical practitioners, to be followed by a two-week summer course for CME credit on evolutionary medicine;
- Development and dissemination of a standardized “slide set” on human evolution to be made available to biology faculty and instructors free of charge
- Darwin Day activities in partnership with the North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences that included a public talk by an internationally known expert on shark evolution, and a day-long public outreach event at the museum.
- Also, as part of a public outreach event in collaboration with the North Carolina Science Festival and the North

Carolina School of Science and Math, NESCent will be co-hosting an evening stage performance by hip hop artist Baba Brinkman, notable for “The Rap Guide to Evolution.” The event is free and open to the public and will take place Friday, September 24, 2010.

3.1.2 Outreach to the science community

In order to identify gaps in existing short courses on evolution and evolutionary informatics topics, we solicited course ideas from the evolution community at large. We then conducted open, online voting to rank topics and held an open call for proposals for the most highly prioritized courses to be supported by NESCent.

We continued to organize and conduct a weekly seminar series for in-house scientists and invited speakers from the local (NC Triangle) area. We also introduced a new seminar series (The “NESCent Director’s Seminar”) to bring in more diverse speakers from the Triangle area and beyond.

3.1.3 Outreach to underrepresented minorities

We continued to organize and run a collection of evolution outreach activities at the annual SACNAS (Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science) conference. We once again collaborated with Scott Edwards (Harvard) and Rich Kliman (Cedar Crest College) on the Undergraduate Diversity at Evolution program, which sends 25 undergraduates to the annual Evolution (SSE/SSB/ASN) conference and provides them with mentoring and professional development while there.

We continued the NESCent MSI Faculty Travel Award program, which sends up to three faculty members from minority serving institutions to a national evolution conference to present original research. We also strengthened efforts to solicit proposals for targeted sabbaticals for MSI faculty, and as a result anticipate having one of these positions filled for the 2010-11 academic year.

We met with Joe Graves, the chair of our Advisory Board, to discuss how we may strengthen our mission to MSI students and faculty. Representation of underrepresented minorities in our scientific programs remains poor (see Assessment section), and the prime reason for this appears to be a lack of time to pursue research. We are frustrated that we cannot engage underrepresented minorities in our programs, and we would welcome advice on this.

In addition, we organized and hosted a meeting of Education, Outreach and Communications staff from the NSF funded synthesis centers (NESCent, NCEAS, NIMBioS, iPlant) as well as NEON, BioSynC (the Biodiversity Synthesis Center) and AIBS to explore possible areas of overlap and potential collaboration and leveraging of efforts. Based on the productivity of this first effort, it was decided that this will be done annually, with a different center hosting the meeting each year.

(EDUCATION AND OUTREACH, cont'd.)

3.1.4 Informatics courses

NESCent continues to offer courses on informatics topics. Those that were sponsored, cosponsored, or hosted in 2010 have collectively reached well over 100 students around the world:

- A three-day one-time Regression and Classification Tree Workshop organized by and offered to resident scientists, taught by Richard Cutler of Utah State University.
- GMOD Summer School. A recurring 4-day course held at NESCent for power users of the Generic Model Organism Database toolkit, taught by a team of instructors, hosted by NESCent, and organized by our informatics staff (through funding from NIH)
- The Comparative Methods and Macroevolution In R Summer Short Course, a 5-day workshop hosted by NCEAS, cosponsored by NESCent, and organized by Michael Alfaro and Luke Harmon.
- The Paleobiology Database Intensive Workshop in Analytical Methods, a recurring month-long course organized by John Alroy, taught by a team of instructors, held at Macquarie University in Sydney, and sponsored by The Paleontological Society and NESCent.
- Computational Phyloinformatics, a recurring two-week course hosted this year, for the first time, at the Beijing Genomics Institute in Shenzhen, China, organized by William Piel and cosponsored by NESCent. This is NESCent's longest running course, having grown out of the 2006 Phyloinformatics Hackathon and offered every year since.

3.2 Year 7 Activities

In the coming year, we will continue to offer the collection of activities and education/outreach resources upon which our solid foundation is built. In addition, there are several exciting new initiatives which will allow us to broaden our impact locally, nationally and internationally. These include the following.

3.2.1 The NESCent Ambassador Program

This is an effort to increase our international outreach efforts by sharing and transferring expertise to institutions and individuals outside of the United States that possess data (or access to data), but may lack methods, processes and expertise for analyzing these data. The Ambassadorships also open the door to ongoing collaborations amongst scientists. Ambassadors (current and past NESCent scientists) will serve one-week to one-month ambassadorships. Our goal for Year 7 is to complete three ambassadorships (in Kenya, Colombia and Indonesia) as a proof-of-concept, with a goal of expanding the number and breadth of ambassadorships in subsequent years.

3.2.2 MSI Guest Lectureship Program

In an effort to advance both our minority outreach and postdoctoral professional development efforts, we will begin supporting postdoctoral visits to minority serving institutions to deliver guest lectures, as well as information to minority undergraduates on graduate opportunities and careers in evolutionary biology, and to make MSI faculty aware of opportunities for NESCent support of their research and education efforts.

3.2.3 Darwin Day

For the last several years, NESCent's Darwin Day efforts, while successful, have served primarily a local/regional audience. In Year 7 we will begin to serve a national audience by organizing multiple "satellite events" in mid-sized to smaller communities around the country that would not otherwise have access to Darwin Day activities. We anticipate involvement from current and past NESCent scientists in these activities, which would be organized in cooperation with local teachers who have demonstrated an interest in evolution education and outreach.

4. INFORMATICS

4.1 Year 6 activities

In the past year, NESCent has expanded its capacity for supporting sponsored science and continued to engage in a variety of community-oriented cyberinfrastructure and training initiatives.

We are pleased to have recruited Dr. Karen Cranston to serve as the Training Coordinator and Bioinformatics Project Manager starting in October 2010. In this new position, she will take responsibility for coordinating NESCent's growing summer course and internship programs, and for making sure NESCent's informatics program is meeting the needs of both visiting and resident scientists.

A new dedicated video-conference room has been installed in our Grey Building expansion space. The room has capacity for 5 local participants in panel orientation, or 14 in conference orientation, and can support two simultaneous presentations. It has touch panel control 4 large LCD screens, 3 cameras, and 2 ceiling microphones. It is equipped with high-fidelity sound and advanced echo cancellation, as well as web- and videoconferencing capabilities. The room greatly improves the center's ability to support remote collaboration, and is already seeing heavy use, especially by informatics staff.

4.1.1 Database products in support of working groups

Major informatics projects done in collaboration with NESCent scientists and staff include the following:

- The Primate Life History Database (<http://plhdb.org> or <http://demo.plhdb.org>) was developed in collaboration between NESCent staff and the "Primate Life Histories" Working Group. Version 1.0, released in June, is described in a methods publication (Strier, K., J. Altmann, et al. (2010). "The Primate Life History Database: A unique shared ecological data resource." *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 1:199-211). The database contains decades of individual-based life history data that have been collected from multiple wild primate populations, enabling comparative analyses of population dynamics and the social and ecological adaptations that have shaped primate evolution. The source code for the database is distributed through Sourceforge and GitHub.
- The Mammalian Feeding Database (<http://feeding.nescent.org>) enables comparative analysis of data on craniofacial and neuromuscular motor function across dozens of mammalian species, in order to address questions about the evolution, functional morphology, and development of the mammalian head and its role in feeding. Working group members aim to use this resource to preserve and synthesize decades of electromyography and sonomicrometry experiments, as well as data on kinematic movements, strain, and bite force. The PIs

submitted an NSF ABI proposal in August to further develop this database as a community resource.

- We have undertaken a major new collaboration with the working group on "Evolutionary shifts in vertebrate visual ecology and visual system morphology," which is assembling a dataset from the literature describing variation in about 50 visual system traits within the extant vertebrates. This has led to a fruitful collaboration with the Phenoscope project (<http://phenoscope.org>) to jointly build a more comprehensive and useful vertebrate taxonomic ontology.

4.1.2 Informatics products from sponsored scientists

A number of resident scientists have developed important software or data products in the course of their work:

- Postdoctoral fellow Ben Redelings continues to contribute to updates of the Bali-Phy package for simultaneous Bayesian inference of alignment and phylogeny (<http://www.biomath.ucla.edu/msuchard/bali-phy>).
- Recently departed postdoctoral fellow Stephen Smith has made a number of contributions to software packages for large-scale phylogenetic and phylogeographic inference, including PHLAWD, Lagrange and Phyx (<http://blackrim.org/programs>).
- Several short-term visitors have had projects that involved fruitful collaborations with informatics. A notable example is a visit from Frans Plooi, who digitized and translated a rare collection of field notes on chimpanzee vocal communication in the wild, collected by Dr. Plooi and late Hetty van de Rijt-Plooi at Gombe in the early seventies. Informatics staff have been assisting Dr. Plooi in making these notes available to the wider research community.

4.1.3 Enhancement of community resources

NESCent is now host to TreeBASE, a repository of thousands of published phylogenetic trees and the data used to generate them. The March 2010 release of the database was a ground-up redesign by the CIPRES project, with contributions from the NESCent EvoInformatics Working group, center informatics staff, and others.

Mesquite is a graphical application for phylogenetic and evolutionary analysis while R is a system for statistical computation primarily oriented around text-based programming. Leveraging the strengths of both tools, communication in both directions is now possible through a Beta release, in January 2010, of software that was originally conceived at a NESCent hackathon in 2007.

A Phyloinformatics Research Foundation has been established to provide organizational stability and strategic oversight to important community phyloinformatics

(INFORMATICS, cont'd.)

resources, specifically the Tree of Life Web Project (<http://tolweb.org>) and TreeBASE (described above). The foundation is a not-for-profit officially registered in Connecticut. The initial meeting of the foundation board, which includes Karen Cranston, is being scheduled for this fall at NESCent.

4.1.4 Informatics Training

For the 4th year in a row, NESCent served as a mentoring organization in the Google Summer of Code. With financial support from Google, six students worked remotely with mentors over the summer on open-source, collaborative software development projects: (https://www.nescent.org/wg_phyloinformatics/Phyloinformatics_Summer_of_Code_2010).

Additional internships in information science and informatics were sponsored through the NSF INTEROP Virtual Data Center project. NESCent-DataONE postdoctoral fellow Heather Piwowar mentored three graduate student summer interns on a group project exploring the limitations of current policies around data citation and data management, at the same time experimenting with open-notebook science: http://openwetware.org/wiki/DataONE:Notebook/Summer_2010.

4.1.5 Informatics Workshops and Conferences

NESCent served as host or organizer for several important cyberinfrastructure workshops, symposia and conferences in the past year, including:

- The inaugural iEvoBio conference was held in conjunction with the annual Evolution Meetings in Portland in order to promote collaborative, open-source software development in the fields of evolution and biodiversity; it had over 300 registrants..
- Two NSF-funded workshops solicited and synthesized community input around a National Integrated Biocollections Alliance, an initiative to develop and implement a strategic plan for the digitization and mobilization of biocollections data (<http://digbiocol.wordpress.com>).
- A hosted workshop bringing together multiple groups developing anatomy ontologies for fish, herps, and mammals in order to develop a new, shared vertebrate-wide skeletal ontology, now available in the OBO Foundry: (https://phenoscape.org/wiki/Skeletal_Anatomy_Jamboree).
- Two sessions at the upcoming 2010 TDWG conference, co-organized by NESCent informatics staff:
- One on improving the support for phylogenetic data exchange standards (e.g. incorporation of these standards into tools used by the Encyclopedia of Life): <http://wiki.tdwg.org/twiki/bin/view/Phylogenetics/>

- Another on semantically aware exchange standards for observational data: <https://sonet.ecoinformatics.org/workshops/tdwg-2010-meeting/observational-data-models-tdwg-2010>

- A hackathon is being planned for November aimed at filling critical gaps in the capabilities of the Generic Model Organism Database (GMOD) toolbox that currently limit its utility for evolutionary research. In addition, NESCent staff are co-organizers of the bi-annual GMOD project meetings:

January: http://gmod.org/wiki/January_2010_GMOD_Meeting

September: http://gmod.org/wiki/GMOD_Europe_2010

- A Dryad-UK workshop, cosponsored by the Research Information Network, and held in London in April, with participation from publishers, data centers, funding agencies, and scientists, leading to the funded Dryad-UK project, described below (<http://datadryad.org/wiki/Category:DryadUKApril2010>).

4.1.6 Externally funded collaborations

Two NSF-funded Research Coordination Networks (RCNs) have emerged in the past year from NESCent activities:

- An Evo-Devo-Eco Network (EDEN), led by Cassandra Extavour, which arose out of the NESCent working group entitled “Building tools for emerging model systems in development, evolution, and ecology.”
- A Phenotype Ontology RCN, led by Paula Mabee, Andy Deans, Eva Huala, and Suzi Lewis emerged from a NESCent workshop held in 2009. NESCent has committed to hosting courses and other meetings in support of the RCN.

4.1.7 Other activities

NESCent continues to take a leadership role in the infrastructure for data sharing through its role in the Dryad Digital Data Repository and DataONE projects. With funding from the UK Joint Information Science Committee, NESCent is collaborating with a group led by David Shotton of Oxford University, together with the British Library (BL), the Digital Curation Center and other partners. The group will pilot a UK mirror of the Dryad repository based at the BL, work with major scientific publishers on conventions and tools for publication and citation of data, expand the disciplinary range of participating journals in Dryad, and further develop the business framework for an international organization dedicated to long-term data preservation (<http://blog.datadryad.org/2010/08/06/dryad-goes-international>).

5. SCIENCE COMMUNICATIONS

4.2 Year 7 Activities and New Initiatives

We plan to focus special attention on three areas in the coming year.

- We will review and revise how we provide informatics support for sponsored science to ensure that we are meeting the needs of the scientists, and meeting them appropriately. This includes everything from the technologies used to support remote collaboration to the way in which we build and disseminate custom software products. As part of this effort, we are planning (pending funding) to hold a cyberinfrastructure workshop across a group of NSF-funded and other synthesis centers, to share knowledge, ensure mutual awareness of the goals, resources, and activities at each organization, and identify areas for future collaboration.
- Two, we will be stepping up our activities in building human capacity for tackling future informatics challenges by expansion of the summer course program and enlarging our summer internship programs, both made possible by having filled the new training coordinator position. We will continue our support for the iEvoBio satellite conference, helping to launch that as an ongoing event that supports innovation and collaboration in open-source software development for evolutionary biology and biodiversity. We will be supporting the community-building and training activities of the two new RCNs (described above), both of which have a strong informatics component.
- Three, we will be focusing our cyberinfrastructure efforts on ensuring the interoperability, reusability and sustainability of data. This encompasses a variety of activities, including participation in standards development through our ongoing collaborations with the Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology group, TDWG, DataCite, and other initiatives. We will be pursuing a variety of paths for the organizational sustainability of projects such as DataONE, Dryad, TreeBASE, Tree of Life Web Phenoscope, GMOD. And through DataONE, we will be actively engaged in studying how to overcome sociocultural barriers to data preservation and data reuse.

5.1 Year 6 Activities

In Year 6, NESCent news releases received more than 55,000 page views — an increase of more than 20,000 over last year. They also resulted in more than 40 news articles in mainstream media outlets in the US and elsewhere, including Science Magazine, BBC News, MSNBC News, USA Today, Discover Magazine, National Geographic, and NOVA. (For a full list of NESCent media coverage in Year 6, please see Appendix).

In Years 5 and 6 we significantly upgraded our newsletter design and content. We now distribute the newsletter electronically to more than 2,000 email subscribers, and send 1000 to 2000 print copies to academic departments and conferences in evolution and related fields.

To cultivate relationships with editors and reporters who cover evolution and related fields, we also participate in local and national science journalism conferences and events. Smith is a regular attendee at the annual meetings of the National Association of Science Writers and the American Association for the Advancement of Science, and now serves on the board of Science Communicators of North Carolina.

5.2 Year 7 activities

5.2.1 Journalist-in-residence program.

NESCent will offer a journalist-in-residence program as a new part of its targeted sabbatical program. The program would target early- and mid-career science writers and journalists with a demonstrated interest in evolution or a related field.

5.2.2 Conference travel fellowship for best evolution-themed blog

One initiative from year 6 that we would like to continue in year 7 is a blogging contest and travel award for science writers and journalists interested in blogging about evolution. To apply for the award, writers are required to submit a blog post that highlights current or emerging evolutionary research. Winners receive \$750 apiece to cover travel and lodging expenses to attend ScienceOnline2011, a science communication conference to be held January 13-15, 2011, in North Carolina's Research Triangle Park.

6. ASSESSMENT

6.1 Year 6 Activities

6.1.1 Tier 1 Assessment

NESCent's first level of assessment focuses on internal development and evaluation of processes at the Center. This includes whether participants and activities align with strategic plans to increase ethnic, disciplinary, career-stage and gender diversity. A majority of data needed for assessment is collected in the internal NESCent Administrative Database (NEAD) that serves as the backbone for all the Center's evaluative activities. The strength of NEAD rests on data entry occurring from multiple users from center Directors and administrative staff to individual participants in NESCent activities. Virtually every aspect of NESCent's day-to-day operations, e.g. registering for meeting, proposal process, updating the website, require utilizing our web-based interface of NEAD. This ensures that we accurately collect a wide range of data needed for assessment activities with an automated process. For example, we have demographic data on close to 100% of participants in Catalysis Meetings, and Working Groups as well as postdoctoral fellows, short-term visitors, and sabbatical scholars. New features added in Year 6 include:

- A DOI system that provides users an efficient way to report NESCent related publications
- Improving the user interface for participants to ease burden of data entry
- Creating a feature that allows for entry and storage of participants' CVs for use in Tier 3 assessment
- Establishment of workflows to ensure all necessary data are entering NEAD, including improved monitoring and commitment by NESCent staff
- Establishing reporting requirements for all NESCent PI's and participants
- Incorporation of our news office for press tracking
- Developing workflows, templates, and software to ease query and report generation.

During the joint assessment meeting at NIMBioS, both NIMBioS and NCEAS expressed an interest in working with us to port NEAD for use in their own centers.

The appendices provide details of our geographic, disciplinary, gender, and ethnic diversity as well as supported projects and resultant products for the prior year. On average, the proportion of females in our applicant pool is lower than NSF estimates of female graduate students in biological sciences (Figure 2). In terms of offers of support to female applicants for the postdoctoral program, NESCent's percentages are often near NSF's estimates of female postdoctoral fellows in biological sciences. Worth noting is the percentage of offers to female applicants is always in excess of female representation in the applicant pool with the exception of 2006.

Figure 2: Proportion of female applicants for NESCent Postdoctoral Scholarships and proportion of offers to females. Upper solid reference line is the 2006 NSF estimate of female graduate students in biological sciences. Dashed reference lines are the 2006 NSF estimate of female postdoctoral fellows in biological sciences (upper) and zoology (lower).

In the future, we plan to continue to examine our processes and the reasons underlying the weaker representation of female applicants in our postdoctoral pool. For example, we note that female representation can vary considerably among fields, e.g. note that the percentage for zoology is only 36%. In part the demography of pool may reflect the better representation in some pools. Females were PI's of 31% of NESCent's supported projects in year 6 and represented 42% of the participants in NESCent activities (Appendix B&C). These percentages are near those of years 1-5 (32%, 41%).

Minority representation is low for participation in NESCent activities and as principal investigators for NESCent projects when compared to 2006 NSF estimates for faculty representation of minorities in biological sciences. This remains a challenge, and one that we take very seriously (please see Education and Outreach section for strategies and programs we are developing).

In the last year we increased participation at NESCent, and saw an impressive rise in proposal submission (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Representation of ethnic diversity at NESCent in Year 6, amongst self-reported participants.

6.1.2 Tier 2 Assessment

As of June 2010 the number of citations for NESCent papers exceeded 1300 (an average of 6.1 citations per paper). However, simple metrics such as citation indices capture only some aspects of the success of a center. The second level of assessment targets the external influence of NESCent on the broader scientific and education community. As required by the PTC, we are on track to produce a Tier 2 assessment program strategy by the end of Year 7 of NESCent. At the core of this newly implemented program is hypothesis driven assessment (HDA). The use of hypotheses to drive institutional assessment, with a focus on quantitative data and statistical analyses, represents a departure from traditional assessment methods.

Figure 4: Number of proposals for NESCent programs in Years 5 and 6

As a starting point, NESCent will use scientometric and bibliometric methods applied to Center products to evaluate the hypotheses of relevance. Some preliminary examples of hypotheses that we believe are relevant to the goals of a synthesis center are given below. This list allows us to identify what types of data we need to collect, and the appropriate control groups we should use for valid comparisons.

- H1:** NESCent participants publish papers with greater scientific impact and disciplinary diversity.
- H2:** NESCent participants engage in collaborative science with greater frequency.
- H3:** NESCent participants incorporate data aggregation and/or methodological integration into their research.
- H4:** NESCent activities result in the generation of scientific tools that promote analyses, interpretation, and visualization of complex data sets that form the basis of synthetic research activities.
- H5:** NESCent participants continue to use synthetic approaches in their research, after their programs at NESCent end.

Novel assessment presents a challenge, because the expertise to perform and develop new techniques is rare. Consequently, we have devoted some time to identifying potentially fruitful collaborations to assist with assessment of NESCent activities:

- We have discussed the possibility of mutually interesting research on assessment with Chaomei Chen (Drexel University) and Katy Börner (Indiana University), both of whom work in the field of knowledge domain visualization.
- We are also discussing NESCent’s needs with respect to data collection and curation, with Teddy Gray (Duke University) a biological science librarian; and with Amber Budden (NCEAS) a postdoctoral fellow researching publication bias and postdoctoral program assessment.

We have also recruited an information science graduate student assistant, Casey Rawson, who will assist in improving the scope, accuracy and comprehensiveness of the data available for Tier 2 assessment.

In Year 6, we began two Tier 2 pilot studies:

- With Katy Börner, we placed NESCent related publications on a map of science based on a combination of the bibliographic coupling of references and keyword vectors (see Figure 6). Groups of journals characterizing the disciplines on the map were defined using a metric based on a combination of the bibliographic coupling of references and keyword vectors. NESCent placement determined from journal where NESCent publications occur. As expected, we have a strong representation in

(ASSESSMENT, cont'd.)

biological and evolutionary science. In addition, the map illustrates NESCent's broad scientific impact ranging from the social sciences to math and physics. We intend to use this map to build initiatives to promote NESCent to researchers in disciplines that appear to be under-represented in synthetic evolutionary science.

- As an example of Hypothesis Driven Assessment, one hypothesis that we were interested in testing is the extent to which our resident Postdoctoral Scholars collaborate across disciplines and across institutions. A preliminary study comparing NSF Bioinformatics Fellows to NESCent Postdoctoral Fellows is in progress to address this. NSF Bioinformatics Fellows provide

an appropriate comparison to NESCent Postdoctoral Fellows as both programs attract and support high quality applicants. This ensures that the starting populations for both cohorts are similar and that differences between the two reflect differences in the respective programs. Our initial analyses suggest that a slight tendency for publications from NESCent Fellows to contain more coauthors (although this was not a statistically significant trend, possibly because of low power). However, coauthors on NESCent publications were more frequently from different institutions whereas coauthors from papers by Bioinformatics Fellows were from more types of departments within the same institution.

Figure 5: Cumulative citations for all NESCent related publications

Figure 6: Groups of journals characterizing the disciplines on the map were defined using a metric based on a combination of the bibliographic coupling of references and keyword vectors. A three-dimensional layout of the disciplines (groups of journals) places those disciplines on a sphere, which is then unfolded using a mercator projection to give a two-dimensional version of the map. Open circles showing NESCent placement were determined using publications from NESCent supported projects. Size of colored open circles denotes strength representation in that discipline.

6.1.3 Tier 3 Assessment

The third level of assessment seeks to understand the impact that NESCent has upon scientists who participate in Center activities, in order to provide important information about the value of its programs in building communities and in creating a culture of collaboration. The development and implementation of this tier is in collaboration with Dr. Jonathon Cummings (Associate Professor of Management, Fuqua School of Business, Duke University) and is known as the “Science of Science” project. The “Science of Science Project” aims to evaluate the ways that NESCent promotes synthetic evolutionary science. The focus of the project is on the behaviors and attitudes of scientists towards collaboration, and how such behavior is changed as a result of NESCent support. The following is an outline of the formative assessment plan:

- The project targets four NESCent programs: (1) working groups, (2) catalysis meetings, (3) post-doctoral scholars, and (4) informatics hackathons
- Survey data focuses on nature of interdisciplinary research, extent of collaboration, impact of NESCent participation, and generation of new knowledge
- Specifically, the protocol involves interviews and

observations for each of the programs (which has been completed) followed by survey data collection (which is ongoing). The protocol has been approved by the Institutional Review Board at Duke University

- The deliverable for the formative assessment is an analysis of survey data highlighting what factors predict collaboration and novel interdisciplinary research within and across the programs

Since the initiation of the “Science of Science” project in January 2009 significant progress has been made towards completing the data collection phase of the program. The table below notes current data collection efforts and presents an estimated timeline for completing the dataset. NESCent has been collecting this data systematically since September 2009. This increased the data collection effort with 24 of 27 working group and both catalysis meeting surveys being administered during his tenure at the Center. Not only is collection of data increasing with the inclusion of more groups in the project, but also surveys are being administered multiple times to the same groups as they make multiple visits to the Center.

Preliminary analyses of working group survey data (n= 8 working groups who met for the first time) have demonstrated interesting results on the expectations of

PROJECT	# GROUPS	# PARTICIPANTS	#GROUPS	DATE
Hackathons	1	25	4	Fall 2012
Post-Docs	N/A	4	5	End 2010
Catalysis	2	46	4	Nov. 2010
Working Groups	20 (27 surveys)	279 (369 surveys)	25	Spring 2011

Figure 7: Survey data from eight working groups on expectations of outcomes. The Legend represents responses to the question “In which ways, if any, do you EXPECT your NESCent working group research collaborations to differ from your other research collaborations?”

(ASSESSMENT, cont'd.)

participants attending NESCent Working Groups (Figure 7).

- First, participants expect that the collaborations they will develop in NESCent working groups are likely to be different than those collaborations they may have with their advisors, students or other colleagues. In fact, the majority of respondents expect that NESCent-sponsored collaborations will be “Somewhat Different” or “Very Different.”
- Most expect that these differences will be reflected in the types of questions addressed, the disciplines involved, the

grants that they may apply for, and the research methods used to address problems.

- Participants did not generally expect differences in terms of the journals targeted for publication, or the academic conferences they might attend.

We have found that these results greatly vary across the participants and groups. We hope to be able to tease apart the factors that influence this variation in expectations, and how these factors contribute to the emergence of synthesis and successful collaborations.

7. ADMINISTRATION

7.1 Year 6 Activities

In February 2010, Allen Rodrigo took over from Kathleen Smith as Director of NESCent. Earlier, in December 2009, Susan Alberts assumed the role of Associate Director of Science, in place of Joel Kingsolver. As with any change of leadership, modifications were made to the day-to-day operations of the Center. These included:

- Regular (minuted) bi-weekly meetings of the directors.
- Regular (minuted) meetings of the Operations Committee every 6 weeks.
- A new NESCent Management Team comprising the 4 Assistant Directors and the Communications Manager, with regular bi-weekly meetings to oversee operational issues at the center.
- A new streamlined format to the NESCent bi-weekly report.
- A printed quarterly NESCent newsletter.
- Employment of student assistants for weekend work at the Center, to relieve Center logistics staff.

7.1.1 Staff changes

Jory Weintraub was appointed as the Assistant Director of Education and Outreach. With this change, each Associate Director is now supported by a full-time on-site Assistant Director.

Other staffing changes include:

- Appointment of Karen Cranston, as the Project Manager, Training Coordinator and Bioinformatics Support. Karen begins at the Center in October 2010.
- David Palmer replaced Jack D’Ardenne in May 2010, and provides Helpdesk support, video services, and sysadmin assistance.
- Stephanie Risbon joined NESCent as a program coordinator for event planning and logistical support in April 2010

- Accounting Specialist, Julie McAlister, joined NESCent in September 2010
- Candace Brown promoted within NESCent to Administrative Assistant to the Director in February 2010
- Informatics staff, supported by external funds, joining NESCent this year:

Dryad – Dryad Repository Programmer – Kevin Clarke, December 2009

Dryad Project Librarian and Metadata Specialist – Elena Feinstein, January 2010

DataOne Postdoctoral Associate – Heather Piwowar, June 2010

7.1.2 Advisory Board and Oversight Committee

Tony Zera, Troy Day and Bill Piel have agreed to stay on the NESCent Advisory Board for a 4th year. Sarah Tishkoff is leaving the Board this year. We have recruited Fred Nijhout, Richard Ree, Stephen Stearns, and David Krakauer to the NAB, and they begin their 3-year term on 1 Dec 2010.

We are in the process of suggesting names of senior administrators to Jim Siedow, Vice-Provost (Research) at Duke, to be part of the Oversight Committee. The committee will also include the Chair (Joseph Graves Jr) and Vice-Chair (Maria Orive) of the NAB.

7.1.2 Additional Space and Renovations

NESCent continues to grow, both in terms of its resident community of scientists, and in terms of the number of programs it supports. Consequently, there have been changes to NESCent’s physical space. These include:

- Renovation of space for informatics staff and video-conferencing room in building adjacent to our current location in the Erwin Mill Building
- Renovations within the existing Erwin Mill Building to accommodate additional scientists and staff

(ADMINISTRATION, cont'd.)

7.1.3 Information of Outside Services Agreements and Consultants

Consultants contracted during Year 6 include:

- @Mire for Dryad development level support for DSpace installations
- Blue Pane Studios for website development
- Pegasus Info for Dryad planning and implementation of PR and communications strategy, consortium development and repository support
- SciMedNet for Phenoscope web application development.

7.2 Year 7 Activities

The most significant development in Year 7 is the retirement of Karen Henry, our Assistant Director of Research Administration. Karen has been with NESCent since it first started, and her departure is a tremendous loss to NESCent. She will leave a significant gap in terms of her institutional knowledge, and also as a friend and colleague – it will be hard to imagine NESCent without Karen. We would like to place on record our gratitude for Karen's years of service and dedication to NESCent, her collegiality, the degree to which she exceeded expectations in the conduct of her duties, and her ability to remain calm when times are difficult. We will begin a search for her successor in October 2010.

EXTERNALLY FUNDED RESEARCH: NESCent Grants and Proposals

Funded: NESCent-Duke						
TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
Show Me the Evolution! Assessing Effectiveness of a New Teaching Resource	Allen Rodrigo & Kristin Jenkins	NSF-CCLI	1/1/2009-12/31/2010	117,976	117,976	150,000
A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology	Todd Vision	NSF	9/1/2008-8/31/2012	1,400,414	279,551	1,679,965
INTEROP: International Virtual Data Center for the Biodiversity, Ecological and Environmental Sciences	Hilmar Lapp (William Michener)	NSF (Subaward from Univ of New Mexico)	5/15/2008-6/30/2012	39,535	11,268	50,803
DataONE: Observation Network for Earth	Todd Vision (William Michener)	NSF (Subaward from Univ of New Mexico)	8/1/2009-7/31/2014	390,490	111,290	501,780
Helping Interdisciplinary Vocabulary Engineering (HIVE)	Todd Vision	Institute for Museum & Library Science	1/1/2009-6/30/2011	cost share only to Duke Univ		
The iPlant Collaborative	Todd Vision & Karen Cranston	NSF (Subaward from Univ of Arizona)	10/1/10-4/30/11	4,935	1,407	6,342
Supplement: Biological Collection Focal Workshop	Allen Rodrigo	NSF	2/5/10-2/7/10	16,164	-	16,164
Supplement: Dimension of Biodiversity Design Charrette Workshop	Allen Rodrigo	NSF	9/17/10-9/18/10	30,271	1,430	31,701
TOTAL DUKE FUNDED				1,999,785	436,970	2,436,755

EXTERNALLY FUNDED RESEARCH: NESCent Grants and Proposals

Funded: NESCent-UNC						
TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology	Jane Greenberg (Todd Vision)	NSF (Subaward from Duke Univ)	9/1/2008-8/31/2012	258,260	107,265	365,525
A Next Generation E. coli Model Organism Resource	Todd Vision (Jim Hu)	Nat'l Institute of General Medical Science	8/1/2009-7/31/2013	83,411	23,355	106,766
Enhancement of the GBrowse Genome Annotation Browser	Todd Vision (Ian Holmes)	NIH (Subaward from Univ of California-Berkeley)	9/1/2007-8/31/2010	222,218	60,820	283,038
Linking Evolution to Genomics Using Phenotype Ontologies	Todd Vision (Paula Mabee)	NSF (Subaward from Univ of South Dakota)	6/1/2007-5/31/2011	853,338	197,607	1,050,945
Bridge Funds: Enhancement of the GBrowse Genome Annotation Browser	Todd Vision (Ian Holmes)	NIH (Subaward from Univ of California-Berkeley) Arizona	9/1/2010-8/31/2011	59,500	16,660	76,160
TOTAL UNC FUNDED				1,476,727	405,707	1,882,434

Funded: NESCent-NCSU						
TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology	Kristin Antelman (Todd Vision)	NSF (Subaward from Duke Univ)	9/1/2008-8/31/2012	121,042	13,644	134,686
Biological Collections Digitization: Towards Capture and Mobilization of Biodiversity Information Resources	Brian Wiegmann	NSF	5/15/10-4/30/11	35,951	2,518	38,469
CCLI Phase II: Extendig and Enhancing Understanding Evolution for the Undergraduate Community Using Phenotype Ontologies	Brian Wiegmann (Roy Caldwell)	NSF (Subaward from UC Berkeley)	8/1/2009-7/31/2012	22,810	5,930	28,740
TOTAL NCSU FUNDED				179,803	22,092	201,895

EXTERNALLY FUNDED RESEARCH: NESCent Grants and Proposals

Pending: NESCent-Duke

TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
ABI Development: Ontology-enabled Reasoning Across Phenotypes from Evolution and Model Organisms	Hilmar Lapp (Todd Vision)	NSF (Subaward from UNC-Chapel Hill)	2/1/2011-1/31/2015	542,477	131,350	673,827
ABI Innovation: A Novel Database and Ontology for Evolutionary Analyses of Mammalian Feeding Physiology	Christine Wall	NSF	7/1/2011-6/30/2014	86,246	37,803	124,049
TOTAL DUKE PENDING				628,723	169,153	797,876

Pending: NESCent-UNC

TITLE	PI	FUNDING AGENCY	DATES	DIRECT	INDIRECT	TOTAL
Enhancing the GMOD Suite of Genome Annotation and Visualization Tools	Todd Vision (Ian Holmes)	NIH (Subaward from Univ of California-Berkeley)	3/1/2011-2/29/2016	425,000	119,000	544,000
Collaborative Research: ABI Development: Ontology-enabled Reasoning Across Phenotypes from Evolution and Model Organisms	Todd Vision (Paula Mabee)	NSF (Collaborating with Univ of South Dakota)	2/1/2011-1/31/2015	820,722	231,998	1,052,720
The Hymenoptera Anatomy Ontology: Part of a Transformation in Systematic and Genome Science	Todd Vision (Andy Deans)	NSF (Subaward from NCSU)	9/1/2010-3/31/2012	65,946	18,465	84,411
TOTAL UNC PENDING				1,311,668	369,463	1,681,131

NESCent-NCSU: none pending

TOTAL FUNDED	4,521,084
TOTAL PENDING	2,479,007
TOTAL FUNDED AND PENDING	7,000,091

ANNUAL REPORT 2010: **APPENDICES**

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APPENDIX A: Disciplines of Supported Projects in Year 6

Visiting Scholar

Center Project

Course

Meeting

APPENDIX A: Disciplines of Supported Projects in Year 6

	Center Project	Course	Meeting		Visiting Scholar				Total
			Catalysis Meeting	Working Group	Graduate Fellow	Long-term Sabbatical	Postdoctoral Fellow	Short-term Visitor	
Applied Evolution	0	0	2	2	0	0	2	0	6
Behavior or Neurobiology	0	0	0	2	1	0	4	2	9
Comparative Biology	1	0	3	5	1	2	6	5	23
Development	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	2	6
Education	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	3
Evolutionary Ecology or Population Biology	1	1	3	4	4	2	7	3	25
Genomics or Proteomics	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
Molecular Evolution	0	0	2	1	1	3	2	2	11
Paleontology	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	1	5
Phylogeography or Speciation	0	0	1	3	0	1	4	3	12
Physiology or Functional Morphology	0	0	0	2	1	1	2	2	8
Population or Evolutionary Genetics	0	0	4	3	0	3	2	2	14
Systematics or Phylogenetics	1	0	0	2	2	2	8	4	19
Other	1	1	2	2	2	1	4	4	17

APPENDIX B1: Gender of Project PI's and Co-PI's in Year 6

	Catalysis Meeting	Graduate Fellow	Long-term Sabbatical	Postdoctoral Fellow	Short-term Visitor	Working Group	Total
Female	6	1	1	4	6	11	29
Male	14	4	6	12	9	20	65
Total	20	5	7	16	15	31	94

APPENDIX B2: Ethnicity of Project PI's and Co-PI's in Year 6

	Catalysis Meeting	Graduate Fellow	Long-term Sabbatical	Postdoctoral Fellow	Short-term Visitor	Working Group	Total
Do not wish to provide	4	0	0	1	3	4	12
Hispanic or Latino	0	0	0	3	0	1	4
Not Hispanic or Latino	16	5	7	12	12	26	78
Total	20	5	7	16	15	31	94

APPENDIX B3: Race of Project PI's and Co-PI's in Year 6:

	Catalysis Meeting	Graduate Fellow	Long-term Sabbatical	Postdoctoral Fellow	Short-term Visitor	Working Group	Total
Asian	1	0	0	0	0	1	2
Black or African	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Hispanic or Latino	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
White	13	5	7	11	12	26	74
Do not wish to provide	6	0	0	3	3	3	15
Total	20	5	7	16	15	31	94

APPENDIX B4: Nationality of Project PI's and Co-PI's in Year 6:

	Catalysis Meeting	Graduate Fellow	Long-term Sabbatical	Postdoctoral Fellow	Short-term Visitor	Working Group	Total
Non-US Citizen	8	0	1	5	8	5	27
Permanent Resi	1	0	1	1	2	1	6
US Citizen	11	5	5	10	5	25	61
Total	20	5	7	16	15	31	94

APPENDIX C1: Gender of Participants in Year 6:

	Catalysis Meeting	Working Group	Total
Do not wish to provide	1	8	9
Female	46	259	305
Male	204	518	722
No Answer	5	27	32
Total	256	812	1,068

APPENDIX C2: Ethnicity of Participants in Year 6:

	Catalysis Meeting	Working Group	Total
Do not wish to provide	7	42	49
Hispanic or Latino	16	45	61
Not Hispanic or Latino	228	695	923
No Answer	5	30	35
Total	256	812	1,068

APPENDIX C3: Race of Participants in Year 6:

	Catalysis Meeting	Working Group	Total
Do not wish to provide	66	56	122
Asian	36	24	60
Black or African American	0	28	28
White	154	694	848
No Answer	0	10	10
Total	256	812	1,068

APPENDIX C4: Nationality of Participants in Year 6:

	Catalysis Meeting	Working Group	Total
Do not wish to provide	1	8	9
Non-US Citizen	80	158	238
Permanent Resident	10	55	65
US Citizen	160	564	724
No Answer	5	27	32
Total	256	812	1,068

APPENDIX D: Countries of Participant Institutions

ARGENTINA	4	IRELAND	2
AUSTRALIA	7	NETHERLANDS	3
AUSTRIA	2	NEW ZEALAND	1
BELGIUM	1	NOT APPLICABLE	1
CANADA	12	SOUTH AFRICA	1
CHILE	1	SPAIN	2
COLOMBIA	1	SWEDEN	3
DENMARK	1	SWITZERLAND	4
FRANCE	2	UNITED KINGDOM	13
GERMANY	2	UNITED STATES	355

PARTICIPANTS BY COUNTRY

- 355 to 355 (1)
- 13 to 355 (1)
- 12 to 13 (1)
- 7 to 12 (1)
- 4 to 7 (2)
- 3 to 4 (2)
- 2 to 3 (5)
- 1 to 2 (6)

APPENDIX E: U.S. States of Unique Participants' Institution

ALASKA	1	LOUISIANA	1	OHIO	6
ARIZONA	9	MASSACHUSETTS	19	OKLAHOMA	2
CALIFORNIA	32	MARYLAND	7	OREGON	8
COLORADO	10	MAINE	3	PENNSYLVANIA	14
CONNECTICUT	18	MICHIGAN	7	RHODE ISLAND	6
DC	8	MINNESOTA	2	SOUTH CAROLINA	4
DELAWARE	1	MISSOURI	6	TENNESSEE	5
FLORIDA	3	MONTANA	3	TEXAS	5
GEORGIA	6	NORTH CAROLINA	91	UTAH	4
HAWAII	1	NEBRASKA	4	VIRGINIA	9
IOWA	4	NEW HAMPSHIRE	2	VERMONT	1
ILLINOIS	7	NEW JERSEY	4	WASHINGTON	8
INDIANA	7	NEW MEXICO	2	WISCONSIN	4
KANSAS	7	NEVADA	1	WYOMING	1
KENTUCKY	2	NEW YORK	21	TOTAL	365

PARTICIPANTS BY STATE

APPENDIX F: Detailed List of Activities and Participants in Year 6

CATALYSIS MEETING

Evolution of g protein coupled signaling: lineages, constraints, and tempo

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=204

Dates: 5/17/2010-5/19/2010

PI

Alan Jones

Institution

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

CoPI

Etsuko Moriyama

University of Nebraska-Lincoln

Jotun Hein

Oxford University

Joe Thornton

University of Oregon

Participants

John Hepler

Emory University

Stephen Lanier

Medical University of South Carolina

Joe Thornton

University of Oregon

Willie Taylor

MRC National Institute for Medical Research

Todd Vision

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Roger Sunahara

University of Michigan Medical School

Eric Gaucher

Georgia Institute of Technology

John Sondek

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Thomas Wilkie

University of Texas Southwestern Medical Center

Henrik Dohlman

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Brenda Temple

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Joel Dacks

University of Alberta

Etsuko Moriyama

University of Nebraska-Lincoln

Dagmar Iber

ETH Zurich

John Hildebrandt

Medical University of South Carolina

Andrew Roger

Dalhousie University

Laura Katz

Smith College

John M Logsdon

University of Iowa/NESCent

Jotun Hein

Oxford University

David Liberles

University of Wyoming

James Garrison

University of Virginia

Charlie Carter

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

David Robertson

University of Manchester

Stephanie Hicks

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Vsevolod Gurevich

Vanderbilt University

Alan Jones

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

APPENDIX F (continued)

CATALYSIS MEETING

Integrating datasets to investigate megafaunal extinction in the late quaternary

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=205

Dates: 5/26/2010-5/29/2010

PI

Jessica Metcalf 2

Institution

University of Adelaide

CoPI

Rob Guralnick

University of Colorado

Alan Cooper

University of Adelaide

Participants

Jessica Metcalf 2

University of Adelaide

Felisa A Smith

University of New Mexico

Beth Shapiro

Pennsylvania State University

Alan Cooper

University of Adelaide

Rob Guralnick

University of Colorado

Eric Dechaine

Western Washington University

Miguel Araujo

Spanish Research Council (CSIC)

Gary Haynes

University of Nevada-Reno

Adolfo Gil

CONICET-MUSEO DE HISTORIA NATURAL DE SAN RAFAEL

Greg McDonald

US National Park Service

Stefan Prost

Gregor Mendel Institute of Molecular Plant Biology

Christian Anderson

University of California-San Diego

Paul Baker

Duke University

Jack Williams

University of Wisconsin

Grant Zazula

Government of Yukon

Patricio Moreno

University of Chile

Julie A Meachen-Samuels

NESSCent

Corey Bradshaw

University of Adelaide

Jacob Enk

McMaster University

Kristofer Helgen

Smithsonian Institution

John Stewart

Bournemouth University

Andrew Storfer

Washington State University

APPENDIX F (continued)

WORKING GROUP

Costs of phenotypic plasticity and adaptation to novel environments

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=193

Dates: 1/22/2010-1/24/2010

PI

Courtney Murren

Institution

College of Charleston

CoPI

Carl Schlichting

University of Connecticut

Participants

Courtney Murren

College of Charleston

Carl Schlichting

University of Connecticut

Heidi Maclean

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Mary Heskell

Columbia University

Josh R Auld

NESCent

Ulrich Steiner

Stanford University

Cameron Ghalambor

Colorado State University

Hilary Callahan

Barnard College

David Pfennig

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Heather Maughan

University of Toronto

Corey Handelsman

Colorado State University

Emilie Snell-Rood

University of Indiana-Bloomington

Joanna Masel

University of Arizona

Rick Relyea

University of Pittsburgh

Joel Kingsolver

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Sarah Seiter

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

WORKING GROUP

Floral assembly: quantifying the composition of a complex adaptive structure

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=90

Dates: 1/30/2010-2/1/2010

PI

William Scott Armbruster

Institution

University of Alaska-Fairbanks

CoPI

Participants

Stephen Smith

NESCent

Stacey D Smith

Duke University

Christopher Hardy

Millersville State University

William Scott Armbruster

University of Portsmouth

Larry Hufford

Washington State University

Amy Litt

New York Botanical Garden

Lawrence Harder

University of Calgary

Pamela K Diggle

University of Colorado

Peter Stevens

University of Missouri-St. Louis

Charles Fenster

University of Maryland-College Park

Lena C Hileman

University of Kansas

Brian C O'Meara

University of Tennessee-Knoxville

APPENDIX F (continued)

WORKING GROUP

Germination, trait coevolution, and niche limits in changing environments

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=201

Dates: 2/5/2010-2/7/2010

PI

Kathleen Donohue

Institution

Duke University

CoPI

Rafael F Rubio de Casas

Duke University

Participants

Kathleen Donohue

Duke University

Kent Bradford

University of California-Davis

Susan Kalisz

University of Pittsburgh

Amity Wilczek

Brown University

Josh R Auld

NESCent

Jeannine Cavender-Bares

University of Minnesota

Charlie Willis

Duke University

James Clark

Duke University

Johanna Schmitt

Brown University

Liana Burghardt

Duke University

Lawrence Venable

University of Arizona

Rafael F Rubio de Casas

Duke University

Xavier Morin

European Institute of Innovation and Technology

Carol Baskin

University of Kentucky

Jessica Metcalf

Princeton University

WORKING GROUP

Grass phylogeny working group ii: inferring the complex history of c4 photosynthesis in grasses

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=202

Dates: 3/8/2010-3/10/2010

PI

Erika J Edwards

Institution

Brown University

CoPI

Stephen Smith

NESCent

Nicolas Salamin

University of Lausanne

Participants

Erika J Edwards

Brown University

Stephen Smith

NESCent

Pascal-Antoine Christin

Brown University

Elizabeth Kellogg

University of Missouri-St. Louis

Guillaume Besnard

Imperial College

Khidir Hilu

Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University

J. Travis Columbus

Rancho Santa Ana Botanic Garden

Melvin Duvall

Northern Illinois University

Sandra Aliscioni

University of Buenos Aires

Nigel Barker

Rhodes University

Colin P Osborne

University of Sheffield

Fernando Zuloaga

Instituto de Botanica Darwinion

Oswaldo Morrone

Instituto de Botanica Darwinion

Liliana M. Giussani

Instituto de Botanica Darwinion-CONICET

Trevor Hodgkinson

Trinity College

Nicolas Salamin

Universite de Lausanne

APPENDIX F (continued)

WORKING GROUP

Genetic monitoring: development of tools for conservation and management

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=31

Dates: 3/15/2010-3/19/2010

PI

Fred Allendorf

Institution

University of Montana-Missoula

CoPI

Michael Schwartz

Rocky Mountain Research Station

Participants

Fred Allendorf	University of Montana-Missoula
Christina Vojta	USDA Forest Service
Jeffrey Stetz	University of Montana
Ruth Shortbull	University of Montana
Michael Schwartz	USDA Forest Service
Kevin McKelvey	USDA Forest Service
Jennifer Jackson	Oregon State University
Dave Gregovich	Southwest Fisheries Science Center
Michael Hansen	University of Aarhus
Katherine Kendall	US Geological Survey Glacier Field Station
David Tallmon	University of Alaska-Southeast
Nils Ryman	Stockholm University
Maile Neel	University of Maryland-College Park (MD)
Robin Waples	Northwest Fisheries Science Center
Don Waller	University of Wisconsin-Madison
Linda Laikre	Stockholm University
Isabelle Olivieri	Universite de Montpellier II

WORKING GROUP

Building tools for emerging model systems in development, evolution, and ecology

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=91

Dates: 3/26/2010-3/27/2010

PI

Elena M Kramer

Institution

Harvard University

CoPI

Participants

Antônia Monteiro	Yale University
David Clements	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Mike Shapiro	University of Utah
Bob Freeman	Harvard Medical School
Todd Vision	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Cassandra Extavour	Harvard University
Andrew Groover	University of California-Davis
Thom Sanger	Harvard University
Vladimir Gapeyev	NESCent
Yuichiro Suzuki	Wellesley College
Gregory Davis	Bryn Mawr College
John Willis	Duke University
Susan Renn	Reed College

APPENDIX F (continued)

WORKING GROUP

An integrative evolutionary approach to examine sexual selection as a mechanism of speciation

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=194

Dates: 3/27/2010–3/28/2010

PI

Rebecca Safran

Institution

University of Colorado

CoPI

Albert Uy

Syracuse University

Participants

Rebecca Safran

University of Colorado

Albert Uy

Syracuse University

Maria R Servedio

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Alicia Frame

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

David Gray

California State University-Northridge

Laurel Symes

Dartmouth College

Dustin Rubenstein

Columbia University

Eileen Hebets

University of Nebraska

Rafael Rodriguez

University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee

Patrik Nosil

University of Colorado

Michael Kopp

University of Vienna

Jenny Boughman

Michigan State University

Sander Van Doorn

University of Berne

Tamra Mendelson

University of Maryland-Baltimore County

WORKING GROUP

Communicating the relevance of human evolution

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=203

Dates: 4/9/2010–4/11/2010

PI

Norman Johnson

Institution

University of Massachusetts-Amherst

CoPI

James J Smith

Michigan State University

Louise Mead

National Center for Science Education

Participants

Norman Johnson

University of Massachusetts-Amherst

Ann Demogines

University of Texas-Austin

Rebecca Jordan

Rutgers University

Briana Pobiner

Smithsonian Institution

James J Smith

Michigan State University

David Hillis

University of Texas-Austin

Louise Mead

National Center for Science Education

Chelsea Crawford

Monta Vista High School

T. Ryan Gregory

University of Guelph

Lauri Lebo

Independent Journalist

Robin A Smith

NESCent

Kristin Jenkins

NESCent

Jory P Weintraub

NESCent

John M Logsdon

University of Iowa

Randolph Nesse

University of Michigan-Ann Arbor

APPENDIX F (continued)

WORKING GROUP

Evolution and development of polyphenisms: pathways to innovation and diversification

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=149

Dates: 5/12/2010-5/14/2010

PI

David Pfennig

Institution

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

CoPI

Armin Moczek

Indiana University-Bloomington

Participants

David Pfennig

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Ehab Abouheif

McGill University

Mary Jane West-Eberhard

Smithsonian Institute

Sonia E Sultan

Wesleyan University

Armin Moczek

University of Indiana

Ian Dworkin

Michigan State University

Tami Cruickshank

University of Indiana

Carl Schlichting

University of Connecticut

Emilie Snell-Rood

Indiana University-Bloomington

Matthew Wund

The College of New Jersey

Cris C Ledon-Rettig

University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Susan Foster

Clark University

WORKING GROUP

Measuring evolutionary change in modern human populations using cohort data

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=27

Dates: 5/21/2010-5/21/2010

PI

Diddahally Govindaraju

Institution

Boston University

CoPI

Andrew Clark

Cornell University

Stephen Stearns

Yale University

Trudy Mackay

North Carolina State University

Participants

Diddahally Govindaraju

Boston University

Charles J Goodnight

University of Vermont

Randolph Nesse

University of Michigan

Stephen Stearns

Yale University

Dorian Garrick

Iowa State University

Trudy Mackay

North Carolina State University

Douglas Ewbank

University of Pennsylvania

Anatoliy Yashin

Duke University

Shamil Sunyaev

Brigham & Women's Hospital and Harvard Medical School

Jacob Moorad

University of Georgia

APPENDIX F (continued)

WORKING GROUP

Analysis and synthesis of physiologic data from the mammalian feeding apparatus

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=150

Dates: 5/20/2010-5/21/2010

PI

Christine Wall

Institution

Duke University

CoPI

Chris Vinyard
Medicine and Pharmacy
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Duke University
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Harvard University
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ACTA
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University of Washington
University of Antwerp
Duke University
Ohio University
Ohio University
University of Illinois (Chicago)
NEOUCOM
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King's College London

WORKING GROUP

Floral assembly: quantifying the composition of a complex adaptive structure

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=90

Dates: 6/8/2010-6/10/2010

PI

Charles Fenster

Institution

University of Maryland-University College

CoPI

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Stacey D Smith
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Michael Alfaro
Lena C Hileman
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University of Tennessee-Knoxville
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University of Kansas
University of Maryland-College Park
University of Portsmouth
University of Colorado
Washington State University
University of Missouri-St. Louis
Millersville State University
New York Botanical Garden

APPENDIX F (continued)

WORKING GROUP

Montane diversity in space and time: linking evolutionary biology and macroecology

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=30

Dates: 6/14/2010-6/18/2010

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Jeremy VanDerWal
Ana Carnaval
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University of Minnesota-Twin Cities
Cornell University
University California-Berkeley
University California-Berkeley
NESCent
Universidad de los Andes
James Cook University
The City College, City University of New York
State University of New York-Stony Brook
NESCent

WORKING GROUP

Evolutionary shifts in vertebrate visual ecology and visual system morphology

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=192

Dates: 6/21/2010-6/24/2010

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CoPI

Christopher Heesy
Andrew Iwaniuk
Neuroscience

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Jason Kamilar
Nathaniel Dominy
Bret Moore
Eric Warrant
Esteban Fernandez-Juricic
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Shaun P. Collin
Ellis Loew

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University of Alberta
Dartmouth College
Midwestern University
University of California, San Diego
Yale University
University of California, Santa Cruz
Purdue University
University of Lund, Sweden
Purdue University
Harvard University
University of Western Australia, Australia
Cornell University

APPENDIX F (continued)

WORKING GROUP

Software for bayesian evolutionary analysis by sampling trees

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=191

Dates: 6/30/2010-7/2/2010

PI

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University of Auckland

CoPI

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University of Washington
Duke University and NESCent
New York University School of Medicine (New York, NY)
North Carolina State University
Florida State University
University of Edinburgh
University of Maryland-College Park
University of California-Davis
University of California-Los Angeles
NESCent

WORKING GROUP

Integrating evolutionary theory with behavioral economics

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=219

Dates: 8/27/2010-8/28/2010

PI

CoPI

David Wilson
John Gowdy

Institution

Binghamton University
Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Participants

David Wilson
Janet Landa
David Rand
Robert Kurzban
Eva van den Broek
Bruce Wexler
Greg DeAngelo
Alex Rosenberg
Daniel Nettle
Robert Kadar
Ulrich Witt
Michael Cox
John Gowdy
Dennis Embry

Binghamton University
York University
Harvard University
University of Pennsylvania
University of Amsterdam
Yale University
Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute
Duke University
Newcastle University
Binghamton University
Max Planck Institute of Economics
Indiana University
Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute
PAXIS Institute

APPENDIX F (continued)

WORKING GROUP

Software for bayesian evolutionary analysis by sampling trees

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=191

Dates: 6/30/2010-7/2/2010

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Greg DeAngelo
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York University
Harvard University
University of Pennsylvania
University of Amsterdam
Yale University
Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute
Duke University
Newcastle University
Binghamton University
Max Planck Institute of Economics
Indiana University
Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute
PAXIS Institute

APPENDIX F (continued)

WORKING GROUP

Analysis and synthesis of physiologic data from the mammalian feeding apparatus

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=150

Dates: 8/30/2010-9/1/2010

PI

Christine Wall

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University of Washington
University of Antwerp
Duke University
Ohio University
Ohio University
University of Illinois (Chicago)
NEOUCOM
Duke University
King's College London

APPENDIX G: Publications from NESCent Supported Projects in Year 6

Catalysis Meeting	
Erika J Edwards Colin P Osborne Caroline A E Stromberg	Edwards, E. and S. Smith (2010). "Phylogenetic analyses reveal the shady history of C4 grasses" <i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences</i> .
Roy Plotnick	Plotnick, R. E., S.Q. Dornbos, and J. Chen 2010 Information landscapes and sensory ecology of the Cambrian Radiation. <i>Paleobiology</i> 36: 303-317
Cynthia M Beall Peter Robbins	Beall et al. 2010 Natural selection on EPAS1 (HIF2-alpha) associated with low hemoglobin concentration in Tibetan highlanders. <i>PNAS</i> 107:11459-11464
Massimo Pigliucci Christina L Richards Oliver Bossdorf	Christina L. Richards, Oliver Bossdorf and Massimo Pigliucci. 2010, What Role Does Heritable Epigenetic Variation Play in Phenotypic Evolution?, <i>BioScience</i> , volume 60, issue 3, pp. 232-237

Long-term Sabbatical	
Douglas Eernisse	Eernisse, D., M. Strathmann and R. Strathmann. 2010. <i>Henricia pumila</i> sp. nov.: A brooding seastar (Asteroidea) from the coastal northeastern Pacific. <i>Zootaxa</i> 2329: 22-36.
Michael S Rosenberg	Rosenberg, M.S. 2010. A Generalized Formula for Converting Chi-Square Tests to Effect Sizes for Meta-Analysis. <i>PLoS ONE</i> 5(4):e10059.
James H Hunt	James H. Hunt, Florian Wolschin, Michael T. Henshaw, Thomas C. Newman, Amy L. Toth, and Gro V. Amdam. 2010, Differential Gene Expression and Protein Abundance Evince Ontogenetic Bias toward Castes in a Primitively Eusocial Wasp, <i>PLoS ONE</i> , volume 5, issue 5, pp. e10674
Elizabeth Lacey	Elizabeth P. Lacey, Mary E. Lovin, Scott J. Richter and Dean A. Herington. 2010, Floral Reflectance, Color, and Thermoregulation: What Really Explains Geographic Variation in Thermal Acclimation Ability of Ectotherms?, <i>The American Naturalist</i> , volume 175, issue 3, pp. 335-349
Michael S Rosenberg	Manel, S., Joost, S., Epperson, B.K., Holderegger, R., Storer, A., Rosenberg, M.S., Scribner, K., Bonin, A. & Fortin, M.-J. (2010) Perspectives on the use of landscape genetics to detect genetic adaptive variation in the field. <i>Molecular Ecology</i> , 19, 3760-3772.
Michael S Rosenberg	Epperson, B.K., McRae, B.H., Scribner, K., Cushman, S.A., Rosenberg, M.S., Fortin, M.-J., James, P.M.A., Murphy, M., Manel, S., Legendre, P. & Dale, M.R.T. (2010) Utility of computer simulations in landscape genetics. <i>Molecular Ecology</i> , 19, 3549-3564.
Michael S Rosenberg	Anderson, C.D., Epperson, B.K., Fortin, M.-J., Holderegger, R., James, P., Rosenberg, M.S., Scribner, K.T. & Spear, S. (2010) Considering spatial and temporal scale in landscape-genetic studies of gene flow. <i>Molecular Ecology</i> . 19. 3565-3575.

APPENDIX G (continued)

Postdoctoral Fellow	
Stephen Smith	Edwards, E. and S. Smith (2010). "Phylogenetic analyses reveal the shady history of C4 grasses." <i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences</i> .
Josh R Auld	Auld, J. R., and R. A. Relyea. 2010. Life-history plasticity and inbreeding depression under mate limitation and predation risk: cumulative lifetime fitness dissected with a life table response experiment. <i>Evolutionary Ecology</i> .
Liam J Revell	Revell, L. J., D. L. Mahler, J. R. Sweeney, M. Sobotka, V. E. Fancher, and J. B. Losos. 2010. Nonlinear selection and the evolution of variances and covariances for continuous characters in an anole. <i>Journal of Evolutionary Biology</i> 23: 407-421.
Liam J Revell	Lovely, K. R., D. L. Mahler, and L. J. Revell. 2010. The rate and pattern of tail autotomy in five species of Puerto Rican anoles. <i>Evolutionary Ecology Research</i> 12: 67-88.
Liam J Revell	Johnson, M. A., L. J. Revell, and J. B. Losos. 2010. Behavioral convergence and adaptive radiation: Effects of habitat use on territorial behavior in <i>Anolis</i> lizards. <i>Evolution</i> 64: 1151-1159.
Liam J Revell	Lindenfors, P., L. J. Revell, and C. L. Nunn. 2010. Sexual dimorphism in primate aerobic capacity: A phylogenetic test. <i>Journal of Evolutionary Biology</i> 23: 1183-1194.
Carlos A. Botero	Elias, DO, Botero, CA, Andrade MCB, Mason AC and MM Kasumovic. 2010. High resource valuation fuels "desperado" fighting tactics in female jumping spiders. <i>Behavioral Ecology</i>
Josh R Auld	Auld, J. R., and R. A. Relyea. 2010. Inbreeding depression in adaptive plasticity under predation risk in a freshwater snail. <i>Biology Letters</i> 6:222-224.
Julie A Meachen-Samuels	Meachen-Samuels, J.A. and Van Valkenburgh, B. 2010. Radiographs Reveal Exceptional Forelimb Strength in the Sabertooth Cat, <i>Smilodon fatalis</i> . <i>PLoS ONE</i> 5: e11412.
Josh R Auld	Anthes, N., P. David, J. R. Auld, J. N. A. Hoffer, P. Jarne, J. M. Koene, H. Kokko, M. C. Lorenzi, B. Pelissie, D. Sprenger, A. Staikou, and L. Scharer. 2010. Bateman gradients in hermaphrodites: An extended approach to quantify sexual selection. <i>American Naturalist</i> .
Josh R Auld	Auld, J. R. and R. A. Relyea. 2010. Adaptive plasticity in predator-induced defenses in a common freshwater snail: altered selection and mode of predation due to prey phenotype. <i>Evolutionary Ecology</i>
Trina E Roberts	Roberts, T.E., T.R.B. Davenport, K.B.P. Hildebrandt, T. Jones, W.T. Stanley, E.J. Sargis, and L.E. Olson. 2010. The biogeography of introgression in the critically endangered African monkey <i>Rungwecebus kipunji</i> . <i>Biology Letters</i> 6(2): 233-237.
David Kidd	Brian Sidlauskas, Ganeshkumar Ganapathy, Einat Hazkani-Covo, Kristin P. Jenkins, Hilmar Lapp, Lauren W. McCall, Samantha Price, Ryan Scherle, Paula A. Spaeth and David M. Kidd. 2010. Linking Big: The continuing promise of evolutionary synthesis. <i>Evolution</i> , volume 64, issue 4, pp. 871-880
Brian L. Sidlauskas	Harmon LJ, Losos JB, Jonathan Davies T, Gillespie R, Gittleman JL, Bryan Jennings W, Kozak K, McPeck MA, Moreno-Roark F, Near TJ, Purvis A, Ricklefs RE, Schluter D, Schulte li J, Seehausen O, Sidlauskas B, Torres-Carvajal O, Weir J, Mooers A (2010) Early bursts of body size and shape evolution are rare in comparative data. <i>Evolution</i>
Einat Hazkani-Covo	Einat Hazkani-Covo, Raymond M. Zeller, William Martin and Harmit S. Malik. 2010. Molecular Poltergeists: Mitochondrial DNA Copies (numts) in Sequenced Nuclear Genomes, <i>PLoS Genetics</i> , volume 6, issue 2, pp. e1000834
Julie A Meachen-Samuels	J. A. Meachen-Samuels and W. J. Binder. 2010, Sexual dimorphism and ontogenetic growth in the American lion and sabertoothed cat from Rancho La Brea, <i>Journal of Zoology</i> , volume 280, issue 3, pp. 271-279
Julie A Meachen-Samuels	Meachen-Samuels, J. (2010) Comparative scaling of humeral crosssections of felids and canids using radiographic images. <i>Journal of Mammalian Evolution</i> 17:193-209.
Eric Schuettelpelz	Korall, P., E. Schuettelpelz, et al. (2010) Abrupt deceleration of molecular evolution

APPENDIX G (continued)

Postdoctoral Fellow	
Eric Schuettpelz	Pryer, K., E. Schuettpelz, et al. (2010) DNA barcoding exposes a case of mistaken identity in the fern horticultural trade. <i>Molecular Ecology Resources</i>
Samantha Price	Slater, S. Price, et al. (2010) Diversity versus disparity and the radiation of modern cetaceans. <i>Proceedings of the Royal Society B</i> .

Short-term Visitor	
Claire Williams	Williams, C. G. (2010). Long-distance pine pollen still germinates after meso-scale dispersal. <i>American Journal of Botany</i> 97(5)
Roy Plotnick	Andrew C. Scott, Fabien Kenig, Roy E. Plotnick, Ian J. Glasspool, William G. Chaloner and Cortland F. Eble. 2010, Evidence of multiple late Bashkirian to early Moscovian (Pennsylvanian) fire events preserved in contemporaneous cave fills, <i>Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology</i> , volume 291, issue 1-2, pp. 72-84
Travis Ingram	Ingram, T. (2010) Speciation along a depth gradient in a marine adaptive radiation

Working Group	
David Pfennig Armin Moczek	Pfennig, D. W., Wund, M. A., Snell-Rood, E. C., Cruickshank, T., Schlichting, C. D., & Moczek, A. P. Phenotypic plasticity's impacts on diversification and speciation. <i>Trends in Ecology and Evolution</i> (in press).
Joshua Tewksbury Lauren Buckley Robert Holt Michael Angilletta	Gilman et al. 2010 A framework for community interactions under climate change. <i>Trends in Ecology and Evolution</i> 25:325-331
Susan C Alberts Karen B Strier	Karen B. Strier, Jeanne Altmann, Diane K. Brockman, Anne M. Bronikowski, Marina Cords, Linda M. Fedigan, Hilmar Lapp, Xianhua Liu, William F. Morris, Anne E. Pusey, Tara S. Stoinski and Susan C. Alberts. 2010, The Primate Life History Database: a unique shared ecological data resource, <i>Methods in Ecology and Evolution</i> , volume 1, issue 2, pp. 199-211
Susan Kalisz Mark Johnston	Christopher G. Eckert, Susan Kalisz, Monica A. Geber, Risa Sargent, Elizabeth Elle, Pierre-Olivier Cheptou, Carol Goodwillie, Mark O. Johnston, John K. Kelly and David A. Moeller. 2010, Plant mating systems in a changing world, <i>Trends in Ecology & Evolution</i> , volume 25, issue 1, pp. 35-43
Fred Allendorf Michael Schwartz	Laike L. et al.. 2010, Neglect of Genetic Diversity in Implementation of the Convention on Biological Diversity, <i>Conservation Biology</i> , volume 24, issue 1, pp. 86-88
Alexei Drummond Marc Suchard Andrew Rambaut	P. F. Campos, E. Willerslev, A. Sher, L. Orlando, E. Axelsson, A. Tikhonov, K. Aaris-Sorensen, A. D. Greenwood, R.-D. Kahlke, P. Kosintsev, T. Krakhmalnaya, T. Kuznetsova, P. Lemey, R. MacPhee, C. A. Norris, K. Shepherd, M. A. Suchard, G. D. Zazula, B. Shapiro and M. T. P. Gilbert Ancient DNA analyses exclude humans as the driving force behind late Pleistocene musk ox (<i>Ovibos moschatus</i>) population dynamics, <i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences</i> , volume 107, issue 12, pp. 5675-5680
Andrew Rambaut Alexei Drummond Marc Suchard	S.N. Bennett, A.J. Drummond, D.D. Kapan, M.A. Suchard, J.L. Munoz-Jordan, O.G. Pybus, E.C. Holmes and D.J. Gubler 2010 Epidemic Dynamics Revealed in Dengue Evolution, <i>Molecular Biology and Evolution</i> , volume 27, issue 4, pp. 811-818
Marc Suchard Alexei Drummond Andrew Rambaut	E. W. Bloomquist and M. A. Suchard 2010 Unifying Vertical and Nonvertical Evolution: A Stochastic ARG-based Framework, <i>Systematic Biology</i> , volume 59, issue 1, pp. 27-41
Rafael F Rubio de Casas Kathleen Donohue	Donohue, K., R. Rubio de Casas, Liana Burghardt, Katherine Kovach, Charles Willis. 2010. Germination, post-germination adaptation, and species ecological ranges. <i>Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics</i> . In press for December Issue

APPENDIX H: Press Coverage of NESCent Science and Activities for Year 6

General

“Biologists merge methods, results from different disciplines to find new meaning in old data” (*Eurekalert*) http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-01/nescbmm011110.php

“International researchers call out for support of ‘synthetic science’” (*Atlanta Examiner*)
<http://www.examiner.com/science-in-atlanta/international-researchers-call-out-for-support-of-synthetic-science>

Postdoctoral fellows

Josh Auld:

“Scared snails opt for single parenthood rather than wait for a mate” (*Eurekalert*)
http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-08/nesc-ss081610.php

“Scared snails opt for single parenthood rather than wait for a mate” (*USA Today*)
<http://content.usatoday.com/topics/article/Organizations/Schools/Duke+University/05BLeVxONRffH/1>

“Scared snails opt for single parenthood rather than wait for a mate” (*Dallas Morning News*)
<http://topics.dallasnews.com/article/OfCa3iP3Oy3Hn>

“Fearful snail becomes better breeder” (*LiveScience*)
<http://www.livescience.com/animals/hermaphrodite-snails-100817.html>

Carlos Botero:

“Blueprint of the songbird genome” (*BBC News*)
<http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/science/nature/8597808.stm>

“Desperate female spiders fight by different rules” (*Eurekalert*)
http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-06/nesc-dfs060510.php1

“Desperate female spiders fight by different rules” (*US News and World Report*)
<http://www.usnews.com/science/articles/2010/06/08/desperate-female-spiders-fight-by-different-rules.html>

“Male spiders are all bark, female spiders fight to kill” (*Wired Science*)
<http://www.wired.com/wiredscience/2010/06/female-spider-fights/>

“Mindset matters most in female spider fights” (*Nova*)
<http://www.pbs.org/wgbh/nova/insidenova/2010/06/mindset-not-muscle-determines-success-in-female-spider-fighting.html>

APPENDIX H (continued)

Postdoctoral fellows (continued)

Julie Meachen-Samuels:

“Male sabertoothed cats were pussycats compared to macho lions” (*Eurekalert*)

http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2009-11/du-msc110509.php

“Sabertooth just a pussycat next to feline kin” (*The Durham Herald Sun*)

http://www.heraldsun.com/pages/full_story_news_durham/push?article-Sabertooth+just+a+pussycat+next+to+feline+kin%20&id=4368855&instance=main_article

“Sabertooth males were pussycats” (*Duke University Office of News and Communications*)

<http://news.duke.edu/2009/11/sabertooth.html>

“Q: How do you sex a Smilodon? (A: Very carefully)” (*Laelaps Science Blog*)

http://scienceblogs.com/laelaps/2009/11/for_decades_after_its_discover.php

“Sabertooth tigers were relative pussycats” (*Fox News*)

<http://www.foxnews.com/scitech/2009/11/18/sabertooth-tigers-relative-pussycats/>

“Study paints sabertooths as relative pussycats” (*MSNBC News*)

http://www.msnbc.msn.com/id/34026719/ns/technology_and_science-science/

“Saber equality” (*National Public Radio, Los Angeles affiliate*)

<http://www.scpr.org/programs/loh-down-on-science/2010/05/13/saber-equality/>

“Why you should never arm wrestle a saber-toothed tiger” (*Eurakalert*)

http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-07/nesc-wys062210.php

“Saber-tooth cats wrestled prey with powerful front legs” (*Discover Magazine*)

<http://blogs.discovermagazine.com/notrocketscience/2010/07/02/pocket-science-2-1-billion-year-old-fossils-and-arm-wrestling-a-sabre-tooth-cat/>

“Saber-toothed cats strong-armed prey” (*Science News*)

http://www.sciencenews.org/view/generic/id/60839/title/Saber-toothed_cats_strong-armed_pre

“The saber-toothed cat’s true secret: its super-strong arms” (*Discover*)

<http://blogs.discovermagazine.com/80beats/2010/07/06/the-saber-toothed-cats-true-secret-its-super-strong-arms/>

“Saber-toothed cats also had powerful arms” (*MSNBC*)

http://www.msnbc.msn.com/id/38068870/ns/technology_and_science-science/

“Saber-tooth tigers add powerful arms to their arsenal” (*Science*)

<http://news.sciencemag.org/sciencenow/2010/07/scienceshot-saber-tooth-tigers-a.html>

APPENDIX H (continued)

Postdoctoral fellows (continued)

Liam Revell:

“Competition puts the brakes on body evolution in island lizards” (*Eurekalert*)

http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-06/nesc-cpt061710.php

“Lizard camouflage confuses males about gender” (*Wired Magazine*)

<http://www.wired.com/wiredscience/2010/07/lizard-camouflage-gender/#more-23411>

Trina Roberts:

“Africa’s rarest monkey had an intriguing sexual past, DNA study confirms” (*Eurekalert*)

http://www.eurekalert.org/emb_releases/2009-11/nesc-arm110909.php

“Africa’s rarest monkey have bred with baboons” (*NatGeo News Watch, National Geographic*)

<http://blogs.nationalgeographic.com/blogs/news/chiefeditor/2009/11/africas-rarest-monkey-may-have.html>

“Monkey business: baboon may have been mate” (*MSNBC News*)

http://www.msnbc.msn.com/id/33865208/ns/technology_and_science-science/

“Rare monkey interbred with baboons, study suggests” (*LiveScience*)

<http://www.livescience.com/animals/091111-monkey-mates-baboon.html>

Eric Schuettpelz:

“DNA barcoding exposes fake ferns in international plant trade” (*Eurekalert*)

http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-05/du-dbe050410.php

“DNA barcodes could protect plants” (*The Raleigh News and Observer*)

<http://www.newsobserver.com/2010/05/17/485775/science-briefs.html>

“Protecting plants through DNA testing” (*The Charlotte Observer*)

<http://www.charlotteobserver.com/2010/05/17/1440238/science-briefs.html>

“DNA barcodes expose fake ferns” (*Duke News Office*)

<http://news.duke.edu/2010/05/barcode.html>

“DNA barcodes expose ‘fake’ ferns for sale” (*Futurity*)

<http://futurity.org/science-technology/dna-barcode-exposes-fake-ferns-for-sale/>

APPENDIX H (continued)

Postdoctoral fellows (continued)

Stephen Smith:

“Molecular study could push back angiosperm origins” (*Eurekalert*)
http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-03/nesc-msc031210.php

“Stephen Smith: the botanis hacker” (*The Scientist*)
<http://www.the-scientist.com/article/display/57180/>

Gregor Yanega:

“Hummingbirds: Magic in the Air” (*Nature, PBS*)
<http://www.pbs.org/wnet/nature/episodes/hummingbirds-magic-in-the-air/video-expert-hunters/5442/>

Catalysis meetings and working groups:

Erika Edwards et al.: Toward a new synthesis of the evolutionary history and ecology of C4 grasses

“Drier weather 30 million years ago may have led to grass evolution” (*USA Today*)
<http://content.usatoday.com/communities/sciencefair/post/2010/02/drier-weather-30-million-years-ago-may-have-led-to-grass-evolution/1>

Cynthia Beall and Peter Robbins: Human evolution and adaptation to high-altitude hypoxia

“Scientists uncover the genetic secrets that allow Tibetans to thrive in thin air” (*Eurekalert*)
http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-06/nesc-sut060510.php

“Tibetans carry unique genes to combat mountain sickness” (*Discovery News*)
<http://news.discovery.com/human/tibetans-carry-unique-gene-to-combat-mountain-sickness.html>

“Tibetan gene find may help patients in intensive care” (*Irish Times*)
<http://www.irishtimes.com/newspaper/ireland/2010/0609/1224272124849.html>

“Scientists cite fastest instance of human evolution yet” (*New York Times*)
<http://www.nytimes.com/2010/07/02/science/02tibet.html>

APPENDIX H (continued)

Visiting scholars

Jim Hunt:

“The making of a queen: Road to royalty begins early in paper wasps” (*Eurekalert*)
http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-05/nesc-tmo051910.php

“How does a wasp become a queen?” (*Life’s Little Mysteries*)
<http://www.lifeshlittlemysteries.com/how-does-a-wasp-become-queen--0942/>

“Scientists square off on evolutionary value of helping relatives” (*The New York Times*)
<http://www.nytimes.com/2010/08/31/science/31social.html>

Claire Williams:

“Gone with the wind: Far-flung pine pollen still potent miles from the tree” (*Eurekalert*)
http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-04/nesc-gwt040310.php

“Pine pollen gets flight miles” (*Science News*)
http://www.sciencenews.org/view/generic/id/58360/title/Pine_pollen_gets_flight_miles

“Pollen reaches record levels” (*News and Observer*)
<http://www.newsobserver.com/2010/04/08/426997/pollen-reaches-record-levels.html>

“Local researches: Pine pollen pervasive” (*The Herald-Sun*)
http://www.heraldsun.com/view/full_story_news_durham/6987898/article-Local-researchers--Pine-pollen-pervasive?instance=main_article

“Loblolly pine pollen is everywhere” (*Salisbury Press*)
<http://www.salisburypost.com/Health/040710-WEB-pine-pollen>

APPENDIX H (continued)

NESCent leadership and staff:

Allen Rodrigo:

“Penguin males with steady pitch make better parents” (*Eurekalert*)
http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-07/nesc-pmw071110.php

“Fat daddy’s best—for penguins” (*New Zealand Herald*)
http://www.nzherald.co.nz/environment/news/article.cfm?c_id=39&objectid=10659300

“Why penguins can pig out” (*The Post and Courier*)
<http://www.postandcourier.com/news/2010/jul/23/why-penguins-can-pig-out/>

“Humans tested by the speed of cultural change” (*The News and Observer*)
<http://www.newsobserver.com/2010/05/03/464430/humans-tested-by-the-speed-of.html>

Craig McClain:

“When the dinner bell rings for seafloor scavengers, larger animals get first dibs” (*Eurekalert*)
http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-04/nesc-wtd040510.php

“Paradox of dining in deep, wet mud” (*Science News*)
http://www.sciencenews.org/view/generic/id/58558/title/Paradox_of_dining_in_deep,_wet_mud

“Deep sea dibs: When it comes to the worm, the crab is always early” (*Down to Earth Magazine*)
http://www.downtoearth.org.in/full6.asp?foldername=20100531&filename=sci&sec_id=12&sid=2

“Monster bug? It’s no joke!” (*MSNBC*)
<http://cosmiclog.msnbc.msn.com/archive/2010/03/31/2253964.aspx>

“Monster of the deep: Shocked oil workers catch two-and-a-half-foot ‘woodlouse’” (*Daily Mail*)
<http://www.dailymail.co.uk/sciencetech/article-1263042/Monster-deep-Oil-workers-dredge-giant-cousin-woodlouse.html#ixzz0lwBNk3ln>

“Monster from the deep” (*The Sun*)
<http://www.thesun.co.uk/sol/homepage/news/2917518/Monster-from-the-oil-lagoon.html>

APPENDIX I: Active Projects in Year 6

(project titles are hyperlinks)

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
CATALYSIS MEETING				
David Wilson	State University of New York-Binghamptom	The nature of regulation: how evolutionary theory can inform the regulation of large-scale human social interactions	6/1/2009	5/31/2010
Alan Jones Jotun Hein Etsuko Moriyama Joe Thornton	Univ. of North Carolina-Chapel Hill Oxford University Univ. of Nebraska-Lincoln Univ. of Oregon	Evolution of g protein coupled signaling: lineages, constraints, and tempo	11/1/2209	10/31/2010
Jessica Metcalf 2 Rob Guralnick Alan Cooper	Univ. of Adelaide Univ. of Colorado Univ. of Adelaide	Integrating datasets to investigate megafaunal extinction in the late quarternary	11/1/2009	10/31/2009
Richard Moore Tia-Lynn Ashman	Miami Univ.-Oxford Univ. of Pittsburgh	Emergence of gender and sex chromosomes: evolutionary insights from a diversity of taxa	5/1/2010	3/31/2011
James H. Hunt	North Carolina State Univ	Evolution of insect sociality: an integrative modeling approach	4/1/2010	3/31/2011
Gregor Larson Dolores Piperno Michael Purugganan Dorian Fuller Robin Allaby	Durham Univ. National Museum of Natural History New York Univ. Univ. College-London Univ. of Warwick	Domestication as an evolutionary phenomenon: expanding the synthesis	4/1/2010	3/31/2011
Sarah Reece Nick Savill Andrew Read Nicole Mideo	Institutes of Evolution, Immunology and Infection Research Univ. of Edinburgh Pennsylvania State Univ. Univ. of Edinburgh	Evolution of infectious diseases: integrating empirical and modeling approaches	5/1/2010	4/30/2011
GRADUATE FELLOW				
Bret Moore	Purdue Univ.	Do retinal specializations reflect ecology? An evolutionary perspective.	8/23/2010	12/10/2010
Paul Durst	Duke Univ.	Evaluating patterns and trends in insular body size evolution	8/23/2010	12/10/2010
Sarah Seiter	Univ. of North Carolina-Chapel Hill	Distinguishing trait value and trait plasticity in the evolution of reaction norms	8/23/2010	12/10/2010
Nimrod D. Rubinstein	Tel-Aviv Univ. (ISRAEL)	Detection of clade-specific accelerations and decelerations in gene evolutionary rates	9/20/2010	12/10/2010
Luke Mahler	Harvard University	Improving and testing ecological models of phenotypic diversification	9/1/2010	12/10/2010

APPENDIX I (continued)

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
LONG-TERM SABBATICAL				
James H Hunt	North Carolina State University	The evolution of sociality	9/1/2009	2/28/2010
Michael S Rosenberg	Arizona State Univ.	Geography, phylogeny, and population: an evolutionary synthesis	9/1/2009	4/30/2010
John M Logsdon	Univ. of Iowa	Sex, cells: an evolutionary inquiry into sexual reproduction	11/1/2009	7/31/2010
James H Hunt	North Carolina State Univ.	The origins of arthropod sociality	3/1/2010	7/31/2010
Armin Moczek	Indian Univ.-Bloomington	The nature of nurture: how environmental and genetic information interact to shape development and evolution	9/1/2010	8/31/2011
Dorothee Huchon	Tel-Aviv Univ.	Current view of rodent phylogenetic relationships	9/1/2010	8/31/2011
Tal Pupko	Tel-Aviv Univ.	Evolutionary models accounting for multi-layer selection pressures	9/1/2010	8/31/2011
POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW				
Josh R Auld	NESCent	Evaluating the effects of inbreeding on dispersal	10/1/2009	9/30/2011
Carlos A Botero	NESCent	Evolution of conventional signals: from individuals to populations and back	10/1/2008	9/30/2011
Marc J Lajeunesse	NESCent	Meta-analysis and the comparative phylogenetic method	10/1/2008	9/30/2011
Trina E Roberts	NESCent	Sticky tips and misplaced roots: is there a bias in intraspecific phylogenetics?	8/1/2008	7/31/2011
Stephen Smith	NESCent	Integrating species distribution modeling and phylogenetics	10/1/2008	5/31/2010
Julie A Meachen-Samuels	NESCent	Competition, guild structure and evolution in the carnivora	8/1/2009	7/31/2011
Benjamin D Redelings	NESCent	Improved probabilistic models of insertion/deletion for phylogenetic inference	9/1/2009	8/31/2011
Liam J Revell	NESCent	Process and pattern in the phylogenetic analysis of comparative data	8/1/2009	7/31/2011
Juan C Santos	NESCent	Multivariate evolutionary analysis: integrating structural equation modeling and phylogenetics	10/1/2009	9/30/2011
Eric Schuettelpelz	NESCent	A phylogenetic approach to understanding the evolution of the earth's biomes	8/1/2009	7/31/2011

APPENDIX I (continued)

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW (continued)				
Gregor Yanega	NESCent	A comparative phylogenetic approach to the study of insular avian phenotypes	8/1/2009	7/30/2011
Peter Unmack	NESCent	A gis based approach to a priori prediction in aquatic biogeography	8/1/2010	7/31/2012
Jenny L McGuire	NESCent	Examining paleontological extinction patterns to predict modern extinction vulnerability	9/1/2010	8/31/2012
Jennifer Verdolin	NESCent	Integrating behavioral syndromes into social networks: optimal distribution of phenotypes and group stability	9/1/2010	8/31/2012
Clinton Francis	NESCent	Acoustic signal space conservatism: a framework for signal flexibility in noise	9/1/2010	8/31/2012
Rafael F Rubio de Casas	NESCent	Dispersal evolution in the angiosperms: the origin of heterocarpy	5/1/2010	4/30/2012
SHORT-TERM VISITOR				
Roy Plotnick	Univ. of Illinois	Movement paleoecology, trace fossils, and the evolution of behavior	1/16/2010	4/17/2010
Lennart Olsson	Jena Univ.	The origin of evolutionary novelties in amphibian head development	4/15/2010	6/15/2010
Frans Plooi	International Research-Institute on Infant Studies	Translation of field notes for developmental study of chimpanzee vocal communication	3/22/2010	4/22/2010
Claire Williams	Forest History Society	Domesticating forest carbon: a synthesis on forest adaption to climate change	2/22/2010	5/17/2010
Shane Lavery	University of Auckland	Connectivity of New Zealand coastal marine communities: a synthesis of datasets	5/10/2010	7/2/2010
Samantha Price	UC Davis	Evolution of mammalian dietary strategies and the importance of omnivory	8/14/2010	8/27/2010
Samantha Hopkins	Univ. of Oregon	Evolution of mammalian dietary strategies and the importance of omnivory	8/14/2010	8/27/2010
Luke Mahler	Harvard University	New tools for investigating replicated adaptive radiation	7/18/2010	8/11/2010
Howard A Ross	Univ. of Auckland (NEW ZEALAND)	Species delimitation using networks	10/18/2010	10/29/2010

APPENDIX I (continued)

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
SHORT-TERM VISITOR (continued)				
Vincent Moulton	Univ. of East Anglia (UNITED KINGDOM)	New applications of phylogenetic cominatorics	8/16/2010	8/27/2010
Katharina Huber	Univ. of East Anglia	New applications of phylogenetic cominatorics	8/16/2010	8/27/2010
Matina Kalcounis-Rüppell Maarten Vonhof Leslie Rissler	UNC Greensboro Western Michigan Univ. Univ. of Alabama	Potential for peripheral populations to mitigate core extinctions: bats and white nose syndrome	10/1/2010	12/31/2010
Roi Dor	Cornell Univ. (Ithaca, NY)	Applying new phylogenetic comparative methods to analyze character evolution in swallows	8/30/2010	9/5/2010
WORKING GROUP				
Charles Fenster William Scott Ambruster	Univ. of Maryland-Univ. College Univ. of Alaska-Fairbanks	Floral assembly: quantifying the composition of a complex adaptive structure	3/1/2008	3/1/2010
Scott Hodges Elena M Kramer Hopi E Hoekstra	Univ. of California- Santa Barbara Harvard Univ. Harvard Univ.	Building tools for emerging model systems in development, evolution, and ecology	3/1/2008	2/28/2010
David Pfennig Armin Moczek	Univ. of North Carolina- Chapel Hill Indiana Univ.-Bloomington	Evolution and development of polyphenisms: pathways to innovation and diversification	6/27/2008	6/26/2010
Christine Wall Chris Vinyard Susan Williams Rebecca Z German	Duke Univ. Northeastern Ohio Universities Colleges of Medicine and Pharmacy Ohio State Univ. Johns Hopkins Univ.	Analysis and synthesis of physiologic data from the mammalian feeding apparatus	6/27/2008	6/26/2010
Alexei Drummond Marc Suchard Andrew Rambaut	Univ. of Auckland Univ. of California- Los Angeles Univ. of Edinburgh	Software for bayesian evolutionary analysis by sampling trees	6/1/2009	3/31/2011
Margaret Hall Andrew Iwaniuk Christopher Heesy	Midwestern Univ. Canadian Centre for Behavioural Neuroscience Midwestern Univ.	Evolutionary shifts in vertebrate visual ecology and visual system morphology	6/1/2009	3/31/2011
Courtney Murren Carl Schlichting	College of Charleston Univ. of Connecticut	Costs of phenotypic plasticity and adaptation to novel environment	6/1/2009	3/31/2011
Rebecca Safran Albert Uy	Univ. of Colorado Syracuse Univ.	An integrative evolutionary approach to examine sexual selection as a mechanism of speciation	6/1/2009	3/31/2011
Kathleen Donohue Rafael F Rubio de Casas	Duke Univ. Duke Univ.	Germination, trait coevolution, and niche limits in changing environments	11/1/2009	10/31/2011

APPENDIX I (continued)

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
WORKING GROUP (continued)				
Erika J Edwards Nicolas Salamin Stephen Smith	Brown Univ. Univ. of Lausanne NESCent	Grass phylogeny working group ii: inferring the complex history of c4 photosynthesis in grasses	11/1/2009	10/31/2011
Norman Johnson James J Smith Louise Mead	Univ. of Massachusetts- Amherst Michigan State Univ. National Center for Science Education	Communicating the relevance of human evolution	11/1/2009	10/31/2011
David Wilson John Gowdy	Binghamton Univ. Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute	Integrating evolutionary theory with behavioral economics	5/1/2010	4/30/2012

APPENDIX J: Projects supported in Year 6

(project titles are hyperlinks)

CATALYSIS MEETING

Dorian Fuller Robin Allaby Dolores Piperno Michael Purugganan Greger Larson	Domestication as an evolutionary phenomenon: expanding the synthesis
Nicole Mideo Nick Savill Andrew Read Sarah Reece	Evolution of infectious diseases: integrating empirical and modeling approaches
James H Hunt	Evolution of insect sociality: an integrative modeling approach
Tia-Lynn Ashman Richard Moore	Emergence of gender and sex chromosomes: evolutionary insights from a diversity of taxa

GRADUATE FELLOW

Bret Moore	Do retinal specializations reflect ecology? An evolutionary perspective.
Paul Durst	Evaluating patterns and trends in insular body size evolution
Nimrod D Rubinstein	Detection of clade-specific accelerations and decelerations in gene evolutionary rates
Sarah Seiter	Distinguishing trait value and trait plasticity in the evolution of reaction norms
Luke Mahler	Improving and testing ecological models of phenotypic diversification

LONG-TERM SABBATICAL

Armin Moczek	The nature of nurture: how environmental and genetic information interact to shape development and evolution
James H Hunt	The origins of arthropod sociality
Tal Pupko	Evolutionary models accounting for multi-layer selection pressures
Dorothee Huchon	Current view of rodent phylogenetic relationships

POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW

Clinton Francis	Acoustic signal space conservatism: a framework for signal flexibility in noise
Jennifer Verdolin	Integrating behavioral syndromes into social networks: optimal distribution of phenotypes and group stability
Rafael F Rubio de Casas	Dispersal evolution in the angiosperms: the origin of heterocarpy
Jenny L McGuire	Examining paleontological extinction patterns to predict modern extinction vulnerability
Peter Unmack	A gis based approach to a priori prediction in aquatic biogeography

APPENDIX J (continued)

SHORT-TERM VISITOR

Shane Lavery	Connectivity of New Zealand coastal marine communities: a synthesis of datasets
Claire Williams	Domesticating forest carbon: a synthesis on forest adaptation to climate change
Howard A Ross	Species delimitation using networks
Luke Mahler	New tools for investigating replicated adaptive radiation
Samantha Hopkins Samantha Price	Evolution of mammalian dietary strategies and the importance of omnivory
Samantha Hopkins Samantha Price	Evolution of mammalian dietary strategies and the importance of omnivory
Katharina Huber Vincent Moulton	New applications of phylogenetic combinatorics
Roi Dor	Applying new phylogenetic comparative methods to analyze character evolution in swallows
Maarten Vonhof Leslie Rissler Matina Kalcounis-Rüppell	Potential for peripheral populations to mitigate core extinctions: bats and white nose syndrome
Vincent Moulton Katharina Huber	New applications of phylogenetic combinatorics

WORKING GROUP

John Gowdy David Wilson	Integrating evolutionary theory with behavioral economics
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